

Novel Diagnostics for the Cyclostationary Modeling of Temporal-lobe Epilepsy Voltage Records

François Marshall*

Abstract

During a temporal-lobe epileptic seizure: the electric potential induced by somatic local spike firing in cortex manifests cylindrical cortical traveling waves (TRW). These TRW's incur cyclostationarity that neuroscientists exploit to reconstruct a focal seizure source. High between-stratum variability in clinical studies hinders attempts to encode seizures through TRW-sources; therefore, clinicians must often consider seizure characteristics patient-by-patient and epoch-by-epoch. Fortunately, there is a way to validate biophysical models without considerable time and interpretation issues. In particular, two kinds of diagnostic plot are introduced: each overlaying quantile curves for each of the following estimates of measured voltage: a linear, time-variant almost-periodic process; and a process derived from the seasonal autoregressive integrated moving-average class. Quantile curves explain the observed voltage periodicity, reinforcing the TRW-hypothesis: a time-efficient tool to validate the task of finding a focal source.

Key Words: Nonstationarity, Time series, Complex survey, Model diagnostics, Spatiotemporal modeling, Neuroscience

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*Recent Graduate, Queen's University Ph.D. Applied Mathematics.

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1. Introductory Details

Frequently refer to Appendix A throughout the reading of this manuscript. It is an important section that contains: acronyms; and mathematical notation - both manuscript-specific and established. In the section entitled, “Mathematical Notation: Manuscript-specific”: remark that symbols are included in alphabetical order by first symbol listed in the row.

1.1 Manuscript Organization: Cross-section Referencing

Refer to Table 1 for the layout of this manuscript. The reader has freedom to continue through the appendices using this table as far as they wish, depending on: general interest; or the need for rigorous mathematical justification to establish how convincing and reproducible the results of the main text really are. One reads this table left to right, top to bottom - as follows.

1. Columns 1, 2: Section 3 has three subsections (second column): 3.1 to 3.3.

2. Column 3: Lists the three subsections, 3.3.1 to 3.3.3, of Section 3.3.
3. Column 4: Section 3.3.2 relies on Appendices B.3.1 and B.3.3.
4. Column 2: Appendices B.3.1 and B.3.3 are listed in rows lower down the table.
5. Column 4: Remark cases where a section is referenced but not its specific subsection; this means that the section in question has an opening passage, with the labeled subsections following thereafter. E.g., the Section 4.2.1 row states the dependence of this section on Appendix B.3; while the appendix itself has three labeled subsections (listed Column 3), it is the opening passage that is being referenced.

Table 1: Manuscript organization. All parts of this manuscript rely on Appendix A.

		Location		Dependencies		
Section	Subsection	Sub-subsection				
2	2.1					
	2.2					
3	3.1					
	3.2		B.1, B.2.2			
	3.3	3.3.1				
		3.3.2		B.3.1, B.3.3		
3.3.3			C			
4	4.1					
	4.2	4.2.1		B.2.2, B.3, B.3.2, B.4, B.5, B.6, B.7, B.7.1		
		4.2.2				
		4.2.3		B.6		
4.3		C				
5			C			
A						
B	B.1		3.2			
	B.2	B.2.1		B.2.2, B.3, C		
		B.2.2		B.2.1		
	B.3	B.3.1		B.2, B.3.2		
		B.3.2		D.3, B.4		
		B.3.3		D.3		
	B.4		B.2, B.2.1, B.7.2			
	B.5					
	B.6	B.6.1		B.2, B.2.1, B.6.2		
		B.6.2		B.6.1		
B.7	B.7.1		B.3.1, B.4, B.7.2			
	B.7.2		B.2, B.3.2, C, D, D.2			
C						
D	D.1		C, B.7.2			
	D.2		B, B.3.2			
	D.3		D.1, D.2, B.3.2, B.2.1			

2. Temporal-lobe Epilepsy: Treatment Challenges

Symptomized by abnormal motor function, epileptic seizure is a transient brain pathology that is stereotyped by synchronized neuron firing in motor cortex. Epilepsy affects under 1% of the global population, and nearly three quarters of that figure is due to temporal-lobe epilepsy (TLE) [27, 42]. Accompanying concerns arising from the prevalence of this seizure disorder, some of these epilepsies are recurrent and resistant to biopharmaceuticals [34, 33]. For drug-resistant TLE, resection surgery is an important clinical solution; however, success rate remains modest and there remains a high demand for improved understanding of the generative biophysics [7]. To identify a cortical lesion site, neuroscientists employ that low-frequency electrode voltage oscillation which stereotypes somatic, local-spike TLE-activity. This lesion site is defined by the centre of mass (COM) of a 2D cortical region called the seizure-onset zone (SOZ)¹. Clinicians place a microelectrode array (MEA) unto a neocortical layer² that records cortical voltage. The MEA-voltage contains significant low-frequency periodicity: attributed to a neural rhythm called local field potential (LFP). That oscillation which explains LFP evolves as follows.

- Pre-seizure: Limited periodicity (noisy).
- During seizure: Epochs of sustained dynamics³.
 - Type I
Transient electrical pulse: perhaps manifesting a traveling wave (TRW) of somatic, local-spike electric potential. This disturbance type has been attributed to a slow-moving ictal wavefront that affects the cortex on large spatial scales [40].
 - Type II
Prolonged periodicity caused by aggregated neuron-firing activity (not necessarily manifesting somatic TRW's)⁴.
 - Type III
Stable neuron-firing activity: culminating in somatic TRW's.

The second and third epochs are important: TRW's indicate a spatial COM, identifying a lesion site.

2.1 Electrophysiology: Modeling Challenges and Solutions

Columbia University and Massachusetts General Hospital (MGH) conducted a survey including several patients. In this manuscript, one MEA-electrode - designated "Electrode 1" - is considered for each of two patients: designated C5 - Columbia University (C)⁵ - and MG49 - MGH (MG)⁶. For dataset details, see: [22, 40]. As discussed at section opening, neuroscientists identify and localize a lesion site using spatiotemporal SOZ-reconstruction.

¹Remark that a COM only describes an electric-potential distribution generated by traveling waves, and that multiple sources might actually generate a traveling wave [40].

²I.e., a surface whose normal vector is parallel to the electrode axis.

³For details of the described synchronization, refer to [25].

⁴Evidence in favour of the anharmonic periodicity is presented in [22].

⁵The dataset was chosen because the voltage time series exhibits high temporal stability, *viz.* the analysis of [44].

⁶This dataset was chosen because high temporal voltage stability mimics that of the Patient C5 time series.

On the one hand, Type III epochs evince plane, cylindrical TRW's: motivating this localization effort. On the other hand, the Columbia/MGH survey has low per-patient sample coverage given the different spatiotemporal scales of seizure-generating mechanisms. Moreover, the following phenomena together restrict accurate seizure modeling to small-sized strata: sub-cortical noise; and high intra-stratum variability that includes a heterogeneous propagation medium⁷.

Plane waves explain TRW-dynamics; during phases of high-stability equilibrium in MEA-voltage (*viz.*, Type II epochs), a finite cosine-series signal is accurate [19, 22]. If the eigenfrequencies belong to a single narrow band, the resultant superposition behaves like a wavepacket⁸: a narrowduration, amplitude-modulated waveform whose envelope signal determines the spatiotemporal propagation of disturbance information. Under plane-wave hypothesis, [25] employs the wavepacket group phases across the MEA to situate the COM. This manuscript introduces generalized models: accounting for the aforementioned ambiguities in scales, noise and intra-stratum variability; and reducing to said wavepacket model under the narrowband regime.

The models in present work belong to a large model class specified by a decomposition of equilibrium LFP-periodicity in the following two components.

- A sparse cosine-series signal containing appreciable low-frequency spectral content: the output of a nonlinear filter whose input is narrowband.
- A residual signal accounting for cortex electric potential governed by high-frequency eigenmodes - these modes being harder to discern from TRW-extraneous eigenmodes than the modes of the sparse cosine-series term discussed previous list item.

Why this choice of model class? Evidence from past Neuroscience experiments suggests a generative nonlinear stochastic differential equation (SDE) [15, 25, 38, 39, 40, 44, 47]. A particle is used to represent the SDE dynamical system, and it traverses between equilibria: commencing at an unstable equilibrium (Type II epoch), before proceeding to stable endpoint (Type III epoch) [25, 40]. The following two points motivate wavepacket modeling.

1. The solution of the linearized SDE is nonstationary almost-periodic (APR) (*i.e.*, cyclostationary) [47]. Point-by-point on time, the mean of an APR-process is a finite cosine-series signal; therefore, accurate wavepacket modeling is feasible for epochs in which the following holds.
 - (a) The cyclic frequencies belong to a narrow frequency band.
 - (b) The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is high.
2. Consistent with theory in the previous list item: simulation results from [25] and [40] show TRW's appearing during the Type III epoch; the observed effects of weak non-linearity⁹ reinforcing the notion that wavepacket modeling achieves accurate COM-localization.

As the dynamical particle moves between equilibrium points (*e.g.*, the transition from Type II to Type III epochs), one expects changepoints in the dynamical-system parameters (*e.g.*, harmonic frequencies of the wavepacket component).

⁷See the theory in [8] for details on the effects of a heterogenous propagation medium on a concentric-shell charge configuration like that obtained for a freeze-frame of a TRW-system.

⁸Refer to the wavepacket discussion in [22], together with the theory of [12].

⁹*Viz.*, nonlinearity that arises from the driver term in the SDE being a polynomial in a stationary APR-process. See [22] for details.

2.2 Scope and Outline

This manuscript introduces diagnostics for periodicity under the generalized model class discussed Section 2.1. The LFP-dynamics should remain: most stable during the Type III epoch; less stable during the Type II epoch; and least stable during the Type I epoch. How to visualize time evolution of dynamical stability in a meaningful way for clinicians? While the spectrogram reveals structural changes of high-SNR signal elements¹⁰, it is less informative about noise periodicity and low-SNR signal elements. This manuscript proposes two novel diagnostic plots: each containing the quantile curves from a stochastic process that is linear APR time-variant (LAT); and the two plots dissociated from one another by specification of the process finite-dimensional distribution (FDD).

Section 3 presents the generalized model class, and it specifies the novel diagnostic plots. Then, Section 4 shows examples motivating these plots: starting with an illustration *in silico* when it is known that the seizure source produces wavepacket TRW-periodicity; then, demonstrating why the results of the *in silico* data analysis are reasonable from a statistical-inference standpoint; and proceeding to the case of the *in vivo* data aforementioned Section 2.1. Finally, Section 5 draws conclusions and presents future directions. The appendices provide: details of the methods and model-assumption justifications; and definitions and lemmas.

3. Theory

Probability notation in this manuscript is detailed Section A. First, Section 3.1 specifies the survey design. Then, Section 3.2 introduces a time-series model from which are derived novel diagnostics: themselves to be introduced Section 3.3.

3.1 Stratification Design

Four source strata are considered: two *in silico* (different Biophysics); and two *in vivo* (different patients). For each source stratum, only one electrode (“Electrode 1”) is considered because the MEA-responses are highly correlated. As discussed in [19], a seizure voltage record has high data volume; therefore, partition the record (RCD) window, E_{RCD} into stable-dynamics epochs (EPC)¹¹:

$$E_{RCD} = \bigcup_{j=1}^{J_{EPC}} E_j. \quad (1)$$

In Equation 1, the j 'th dynamics epoch, E_j , is itself partitioned into H_j micro-epochs:

$$E_j = \bigcup_{h=1}^{H_j} E_{jh}. \quad (2)$$

Within E_{jh} , LFP-voltage waveforms are broadband: no one single section of the principal domain fully explains the periodicity. To this end, the bottom survey stratum is defined as follows. For $K_{PRT} \in \mathbb{N}$ and $k \in \mathbb{N}_{\leq K_{PRT}}$, partition (PRT) the principal domain as

$$\left(-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}\right] = \{B_k\}_{k=1}^{K_{PRT}}, \quad (3)$$

where the k 'th partition band is itself given by

$$B_k = \frac{k-1}{2K_{PRT}} + \left(0, \frac{1}{2K_{PRT}}\right]. \quad (4)$$

¹⁰Refer to Definition E.1 on signal elements.

¹¹I.e., an epoch of Types I-III.

3.2 The Time-series Model

Consider $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ a time series drawn from the LFP-oscillation. During E_j , the micro-epoch record size, N , is a function of $h \in \mathbb{N}_{\leq H_j}$. Denoting by $\Delta t > 0$ the sampling period: the n 'th time, t_n , is given by $t_n = n\Delta t$.

Assumption 1. \mathbf{x} is realized from \mathbf{X} : a random vector given by

$$\mathbf{X}^T = [X(t_n)]_{n=0}^{N-1}. \quad (5)$$

In Equation 5, X is an \mathbb{R} -indexed stochastic process.

For $t \in \mathbb{R}$, one calls $X(t)$ the t 'th state. The X -FDD is governed by the temporal, stochastic parameter process, Θ ¹².

Assumption 2. Uniformly $t \in \mathbb{R}$: the t 'th state, $\Theta(t)$, is an augmented vector containing $(U_{DST} + 2)$ blocks, as follows.

1. A certain event during E_{jh} , the $(U_{DST} + 2)$ 'th block is $[j, h]^T$. Each of the other $\Theta(t)$ -blocks is a function of the $(U_{DST} + 2)$ 'th block.
2. The u 'th of the first U_{DST} blocks consists of random parameters governing the u 'th candidate $X(t)$ probability-distribution (DST) family.
3. The $(U_{DST} + 1)$ 'th block is a univariate random switching variable determining that of the first U_{DST} blocks whose constituent parameters specify the $X(t)$ probability distribution¹³.

Next, consider the X -components, as follows.

Assumption 3. The LFP-oscillation has the signal-plus-noise decomposition:

$$X = \eta + X^{(RES)}, \quad (6)$$

where the terms are given as follows.

- The cosine-series mean signal, η , is that solution to the harmonic-oscillator equation whose normalized eigenfrequencies¹⁴ belong to B_η the spectral support¹⁵.
- $X^{(RES)}$ is an L^2 residual (RES) process. It satisfies

$$E_\theta \circ X^{(RES)} \propto g^{(TRD)}, \quad (7)$$

where $g^{(TRD)}$ is a nonrandom trend (TRD) term.

¹²The simulation approach is rooted in the philosophy of Bayesian analysis, hence the specification of Θ random. Unknowing of the true Biophysics, the analyst necessarily is choosing different FDD's at random, and must hope that these choices reflect the true FDD.

¹³Appendix B.1 provides a detailed account of the random switching.

¹⁴The normalized version of an eigenfrequency is the fraction of $(0, 2\pi]$ that the angular eigenfrequency spans. The output of the fast-Fourier-transform algorithm is a collection of these normalized frequencies [4].

¹⁵Refer to Section B.2.2 for elaboration on the specific functional form of η .

In this manuscript, it is of interest to consider the signal, ψ , containing X signal elements through the decomposition,

$$\psi = g^{(TRD)} + \eta, \quad (8)$$

Now, consider the class, $\mathcal{G}_X^{(RES)}$, of fixed-lag $\{\Theta = \theta\}$ -conditioned $X^{(RES)}$ autocorrelation functions, where

$$\mathcal{G}_X^{(RES)} = \left\{ \gamma_X^{(RES)}(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R} + t_n) \right\}_{n \in A_{RES}}, \quad (9)$$

with $A_{RES} \subset \mathbb{Z}$ the set of X cyclic frequencies.

Assumption 4. The n 'th $\mathcal{G}_X^{(RES)}$ -element is a solution to the n 'th of N harmonic-oscillator equations: the solution of each sharing a common fundamental frequency¹⁶.

With the $\mathcal{G}_X^{(RES)}$ -specification in Assumption 3, $X^{(RES)}$ is said to be cyclostationary APR. Moreover, X itself is cyclostationary when $g^{(TRD)}$ is constant. A common model assumption in Multitaper Spectral Analysis is that $X^{(RES)}$ is APR regardless of whether it is stationary. Thus, one can imagine cyclostationarity arising from correlations between the X APR-coefficients through the presence of an effect term: a non-zero mean in some or all of the X APR-coefficients when the corresponding $X^{(RES)}$ APR-coefficients are themselves uncorrelated (in which case, $X^{(RES)}$ would itself be a stationary APR-process). Here, $X^{(RES)}$ may well be cyclostationary APR simply due to effect terms in the APR-coefficients; however, there could be other sources like nonlinearity if the APR-coefficients have zero mean¹⁷.

3.3 The Novel Diagnostics

3.3.1 Quantile Curves

The diagnostics include quantile curves: the specific selection of curves depending on the time-series model. In general, it is useful to plot one quantile curve associated with the centrality parameter of the distribution of each time-indexed state. Since conventional cyclostationary modeling relies on assumptions pertaining to stochastic processes whose FDD's are perturbed from the Gaussian, it follows naturally to accompany the centrality curve with two bounding curves explaining FDD-dispersion.

The novel diagnostic curves are derived from the 8D X quantile signal, \mathbf{q}_θ : itself, given on $\{t_n\}_{n=0}^{N-1}$ by

$$P_\theta [\mathbf{Q}[k, n] = \mathbf{q}_\theta(t_n)[k]] = 1, \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{Q} is function of Θ and the p-value, p_X . In Equation 10: the vector, $\mathbf{q}_\theta(t)$, is partitioned into the blocks, $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(1)}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(2)}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^5$. For $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(1)}[k]$, consider the following cases.

¹⁶Remark that a wide variety of stochastic processes have integral representations in terms of oscillations of random stationary amplitudes and nonrandom rotators (e.g., Kalman-filter outputs [4] and state-space models [13, 26]). Discretization of this integral results in a superposition of phasors: an APR-process that satisfies the property of the mean and $\mathcal{G}_X^{(RES)}$ signals being solutions to the harmonic-oscillator equation.

¹⁷When the cause is nonlinearity, each APR-coefficient is a product of APR-coefficients of a stationary APR-driver [17].

- $\underline{k = 2}$
 $\underline{E_{\theta} \circ X(t_n)}$.
- $\underline{k \in \{1, 3\}}$
Respectively: the lower and upper bounds of the 2-sigma region centred on $E_{\theta} \circ X(t_n)$.

For $\mathbf{q}_{\theta}^{(2)}[k]$, consider the following cases.

- $\underline{k \in \{1, 5\}}$
Respectively: the infimum over all $\theta_{U_{DST+1}}(t_n) \in \mathbb{N}_{U_{DST}}$ of infima of candidate $(1 - p_X)$ 100% interquantile intervals; and the same as the $k = 4$ bound, but now the supremum of suprema.
- $\underline{k \in \{2, 4\}}$
The same bounds as for $k \in \{1, 5\}$ in the previous list item, but now the lower bound is the supremum of infima and the upper bound is the infimum of suprema.
- $\underline{k = 3}$
The two-point average of bounds of the first list item, above.

Appendix B.3.1 specifies how \mathbf{Q} has been designed to permit the above \mathbf{q}_{θ} -specifications. Entering through the second block, p_X specifies how wide that interquantile interval should be which characterizes the amount of spread of one of the U_{DST} candidate distributions versus the spread of another.

3.3.2 Reference Dynamic-stability Diagnostics

Motivation

Suppose that: on the one hand, one knows a fixed record size to be assigned the E_{jh} (i.e., the section size is a stratification variable); but on the other hand, one knows neither j nor J_{EPC} . To this end, construct a number of classes: the (j, h) 'th of which is $\mathcal{F}_{jh}^{(\eta)}$, that is given by

$$\mathcal{F}_{jh}^{(\eta)} = \{ f_m : f_m \in B_{\eta} \mid E_{jh} \}. \quad (11)$$

In the diagnostic plots of [19], one finds that E_{RCD} can be partitioned in the E_j according to H_j of the E_{jh} having $\mathcal{F}_{jh}^{(\eta)}$ -COM's tending about a common B_{η} -point. A significant change in this common B_{η} -point marks an X -changepoint. To this end, present section introduces diagnostics that characterize $\mathcal{F}_{jh}^{(\eta)}$ -dispersion.

In this manuscript, the record size, N , of \mathbf{x} has been set large enough to balance: joint-spherical behaviour of the \mathbf{X} eigencoefficient spectra; and computation time. Whilst Section 3.2 specified $B_{\eta} \mid E_{jh}$ as fixed and nonrandom, one can employ a design-based sampling model for $\mathcal{F}_{jh}^{(\eta)}$ to characterize model uncertainty. The analyst has no knowledge of the contributing η_m a priori; even if η was that trendline realized in MEA-voltage from the generative Biophysics, there would remain the uncertainty which of the B_{η} -continuum of eigenmodes had been excited.

The Diagnostics Themselves

Infer the mean η -eigenfrequency using a weighted average: the weights those of a stratified-sampling design on the FFT-grid¹⁸. Denoting by M_N the FFT-grid size, set

$$M_N \in \mathbb{N}_{>N} \bmod 2 \quad (12)$$

¹⁸This design ensures robustness to model misspecification. Recall from Section 2.1 the stratified nature of the joint complex survey.

the size of the FFT-grid in the presence of zero-padding. With only N data points available in E_{jh} , only N of the M_N available η -eigenmode estimates may possibly correspond to physically-plausible η -eigenfrequencies, less the number of inferred model parameters. Therefore: N is the size of an E_{jh} -population of η -eigenmodes; and of this population, only a fraction of these contributes.

For $B_k | E_j$, the following two stratum-mean dynamical-stability diagnostics are introduced.

1. A H_j -vector, $\bar{\mathbf{f}}_{jk}$, of η -eigenfrequency averages: the entries between them tracking the phase of a dynamical particle representative of MEA-voltage during seizure.
2. A $J_{EPC} \times 4$ matrix, $\bar{\mathbf{f}}$, whose (j, k) 'th entry is a weighted average of the $\bar{\mathbf{f}}_{jk}$ -entries. The columns are like the frequency levels an energy-level diagram from Quantum Mechanics: one interprets an $E_j \rightarrow E_{j+1}$ transition changepoint as that dynamic particle from previous list item jumping: from the states, $\{\bar{\mathbf{f}}[j, k]\}_{k=1}^{K_{PRT}}$; to the states, $\{\bar{\mathbf{f}}[j + 1, k]\}_{k=1}^{K_{PRT}}$.

Appendix B.3.3 specifies the exact form of the above two diagnostics.

3.3.3 Data-based Motivation of the Novel Diagnostics

New statistical methods must be backed by rigorous justification: not just theoretically, but through checks on the data behaviour aligning with the behaviour they ought to have for the new models to be accurate. This goes for the X -periodicity anticipated under a hypothesis where the generative Biophysics are nonlinear but the output is modeled by a linearized version of the associated SDE - what this manuscript assumes that justifies cyclostationary time-series modeling¹⁹.

Justifying the Novel Eigenfrequency Visualization Diagnostics

The eigenfrequency visualizations²⁰ are useful only if they are coherent in most of the E_{jh} of E_j . The following three diagnostics inform the benefits of choosing both the $\bar{\mathbf{f}}_{jk}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{f}}$ to identify and explain X -stability states.

1. Spectral boxplots.

- *Frequency boxplots.*

- The E_{jh} -median (MED) H_j -vector, $\mathbf{f}_j^{(MED)}$: given by

$$\mathbf{f}_j^{(MED)}[h] = \text{Median} \left(\mathcal{F}_{jh}^{(\eta)} \right). \quad (13)$$

- The $H_j \times 2$ matrix, $\mathbf{f}_j^{(QRT)}$, whose h 'th column contains the \mathcal{F}_{jh} empirical quartiles (QRT).
- The $H_j \times 2$ matrix, $\mathbf{f}_j^{(MMB)}$, whose h 'th column contains the \mathcal{F}_{jh} min/max bounds (MMB).
- $\mathcal{T}_{jh}^{(\eta)}$ is the multitaper harmonic F-statistic spectrum for \mathbf{x} .

¹⁹Refer to Appendix C on the biophysical justification of cyclostationary modeling given a nonlinear SDE that characterizes the cortical spike firing-rate dynamics.

²⁰Introduced Section 3.3.2.

- *Stationary-phase boxplots.*

The same as the above frequency boxplots, except now with the $\mathbf{f} \rightarrow \boldsymbol{\phi}$ notational change to explain that the replacement has been made of now using the principal-argument class, \mathcal{A}_{jh} , instead of \mathcal{F}_{jh} : the former class defined as

$$\mathcal{A}_{jh}^{(\eta)} := \left\{ \text{Arg} \left(z_m^{(\eta)} \right) : f_m \in B_\eta \mid E_{jh} \right\}. \quad (14)$$

In Equation 14, $z_m^{(\eta)}$ is the η_m -amplitude.

2. *Cepstral boxplots.*

The same as boxplots in the above two list items, except now with the following three changes.

- $\mathbf{f} \rightarrow \mathbf{q}$: the latter symbol containing the quefrequencies.
- $\boldsymbol{\phi} \rightarrow \boldsymbol{\varphi}$: the latter symbol containing cepstral phases.
- $\mathcal{T}_{jh}^{(v)}$ is the multitaper harmonic F-statistic spectrum for that time series which contains log-transformed multitaper $X^{(RES)}$ spectral-power estimates given \mathbf{x} . Here, v is to this estimate time series what η is to \mathbf{x} .

Assessing error propagation

In Appendix B.6 describing the identification and estimation of cyclic frequencies, it is shown how the eigencoefficient spectra of an estimator sequence is required for the calculations. Said estimator sequence contains the log-transformed version of the finite-frequency spectrum of multitaper $X^{(RES)}$ spectral-power estimators. Those model assumptions are now applied to the log-power estimate sequence which are applied to \mathbf{x} to ensure accurate $\mathcal{F}_{jh}^{(\eta)}$ -estimate. Replacing \mathbf{x} by a sequence of estimates has the disadvantage of error-propagation effects. To mitigate this additional uncertainty, a diagnostic quality check is required to ensure that the model assumptions hold valid for the $X^{(RES)}$ spectral-power estimators. If those assumptions indeed hold, then: the $X^{(RES)}$ spectral-power estimators each behave like the scale of a $\chi_{2K_N}^2$ random variable²¹ (here K_N being the number of eigencoefficient spectra in the multitaper spectral analysis); and the variance-stabilizing property of the log transformation does nothing to add to across-frequency variability in the resulting estimator sequence.

Quality checks have already been performed in [19] for the *in vivo* data to be discussed in Section 4.3 forthcoming. Those showed how the $X^{(RES)}$ eigencoefficient-spectra collections for both *in vivo* MEA time-series datasets behave as if they had proper, spherical joint FDD. In Section 4.2 forthcoming, the same quality checks are performed for two *in silico* MEA time-series datasets: the two distinguished by biophysical source. Once again for these *in silico* datasets, evidence suggests that the proper, joint-spherical eigencoefficient behaviour is present. Finding that conditions hold in the *in silico* datasets has the added importance of validating the agreement between *in vivo* measurements and both TLE biophysical models of [25].

In [19], two test statistics are considered point-by-point across the FFT-grid: one for a test of asphericity; and one for a test of impropriety. Consider the probability integral

²¹Remark that the scale of a $\chi_{2K_N}^2$ random variable follows a distribution from the Gamma family [11, 50], and that closed-form expressions exist for the probability density function of the log-Gamma distributions: providing moments that are well-behaved in the sense of boundedness [48].

transform (PIT) of each of the test statistics for the sphericity (SPH) - denoted $F_{jh}^{(SPH)}$ - and impropriety (IMP) - denoted $F_{jh}^{(IMP)}$ - tests. It is explained in [19] that the scatter plot,

$$\left\{ \left(F_{jh}^{(SPH)}(f_m), F_{jh}^{(IMP)}(f_u) \right) : (f_m, f_u) \in \left(-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \right]^2 \right\},$$

displays more information than \mathbf{x} really contains about the K_N eigencoefficient spectra. Suppose that $X^{(RES)}$ were stationary²². Consider $2W \in \left(-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \right]$ the multitaper spectral bandwidth. Given strong correlations of both PIT-spectra in a $2W$ -wide neighbourhood: the following downsampling step coarsens the PIT-grid to ensure near-independent histogram cells. Partition the 2D FFT-grid into $\lfloor 2M_N W \rfloor^2$ -area cells, and denote by $\mathbf{N}_{jh}^{(JNT)}$ the matrix containing joint (JNT) count averages on the coarsened grid. Completing the histogram associated with this coarsened scatterplot, denote by $\mathbf{F}_{jh}^{(SPH)}$ and $\mathbf{F}_{jh}^{(IMP)}$ those vectors which contain the $\lfloor 2M_N W \rfloor^2$ -step downsampled axes respectively associated with $F_{jh}^{(SPH)}$ and $F_{jh}^{(IMP)}$. Now, one has available the histogram from which [19] derives the diagnostic statistics: themselves listed as follows.

1. Denote by $\bar{\mathbf{F}}_{jh}^{(JNT)}$ a vector whose horizontal and vertical components are $\bar{F}_{jh}^{(SPH)}$ and $\bar{F}_{jh}^{(IMP)}$, respectively. Here, $\bar{F}_{jh}^{(SPH)}$ and $\bar{F}_{jh}^{(IMP)}$ themselves are respectively the averages of: entries from $\mathbf{F}_{jh}^{(SPH)}$; and entries from $\mathbf{F}_{jh}^{(IMP)}$.
2. Denote by $\mathbf{p}_{jh,1}^{(JNT)}, \mathbf{p}_{jh,2}^{(JNT)} \in (0, 1]^2$ scaled versions of the $\mathbf{N}_{jh}^{(JNT)}$ principal-component (PC)-vectors (those vectors are designated PC1 and PC2): each scale equal to the standard deviation of that $\mathbf{N}_{jh}^{(JNT)}$ -margin which is associated with the PC-direction.
3. The collections, $\mathcal{P}_{\frac{1}{2}}^{(JNT)}$, of those PC standard deviations which were mentioned in the above list item:

$$\mathcal{P}_{\frac{1}{2}}^{(JNT)} := \left\{ \left\{ \left\| \mathbf{p}_{jh,\frac{1}{2}}^{(JNT)} \right\|_2 \right\}_{h=1}^{H_j} \right\}_{j=1}^{J_{EPC}} \quad (15)$$

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Summary

Because the generative seizure dynamics of [25] derive from a nonlinear SDE, η insufficiently explains the periodicity of Types I and III epochs²³. Fortunately, much of the unexplained periodicity in $X^{(RES)}$ can be explained through cyclostationarity. In the biophysical SDE-model of [25], cyclostationarity arises in the system output: finding this periodicity in \mathbf{x} evinces TRW's because that is what the SDE-simulations of [25] and [40] show. Each $\mathcal{G}_X^{(RES)}$ -element has a cosine-series representation; thus, one reconstructs $\text{Var}_{\theta} \circ X$ using the same simple periodic-reconstruction techniques analogous to those used in generating the η -reconstruction.

In this section, the presented \mathbf{q}_{θ} -plots reveal how cosine-series modeling of η and the $\mathcal{G}_X^{(RES)}$ -curves reveal the E_j - reducing the time a clinician spends exploring TLE-electrophysiology sampling-unit by sampling-unit to establish common source behaviour.

²²Indeed, $X^{(RES)}$ -stationarity is an approximation that makes sense for explaining certain of the FDD-properties in Multitaper Spectral Analysis [18].

²³See the examples in [22].

Additionally, these \mathbf{q}_θ -curves account for model uncertainty. Together with the $\bar{\mathbf{f}}_{jk}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{f}}$, these proposed quantile diagnostics are compared with the spectrogram. In all analyses discussed in this manuscript, $p_X = 0.1$ because it was found during analysis that this choice gives rise to diagnostic plots with conspicuous uncertainty bounds that can be compared across the E_{jh} .

Using the \mathbf{q}_θ -curves, results from the *in silico* SDE data reveal cyclostationarity in MEA-voltage. Therefore, *in vivo* MEA-voltage exhibiting cyclostationarity likely manifests TRW's - reinforcing the notion of a reliable LFP COM where resection surgery succeeds.

4.2 Synthetic Data

4.2.1 The Visual-analytics Product

Two simulations of the SDE-model: one under the assumption of an ictal-core source (left column - TRW's originate from a focal source); and one under the assumption of an ictal-wavefront source (right column - TRW's originate on the ictal wavefront). For each of these two strata, Figure 1 displays the following.

- Row 1: Reconstructed LFP

Black curve shows \mathbf{x} : itself, realized from the $[0, 90]$ Hz-oscillation of MEA-voltage²⁴. Black, vertical lines demarcate the E_{jh} ²⁵. Here, \mathbf{x} was generated as follows.

1. Simulation data was generated using the code of [41]²⁶.
2. The raw *in silico* MEA-voltage series discussed in the first list item was sent through a $(0, 90]$ Hz lowpass filter²⁷.

- Rows 2-3: Diagnostic quantile curves

For model assumptions used to perform the following reconstructions, refer to Appendices B.2.2 and B.3. Refer to Appendices B.4 and B.7 for specific details of the reconstructions themselves.

- Row 2: Gaussian, cyclostationary APR-component of the LFP-oscillation

Same as Row 1, except now: the black curve displays reconstructed $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(1)}(\mathbb{R})[2]$ and the grey curves display reconstructed $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(1)}(\mathbb{R})[\{1, 3\}]$. See Appendix B.7.1 for details of the reconstruction.

- Row 3: Quantiles of the LFP-oscillation, accounting for model uncertainty

Same as Row 1, with the following additions.

- * Inner 1-sigma bounds

The dark-grey curves display reconstructed $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(2)}(\mathbb{R})[\{2, 4\}]$.

- * Outer 1-sigma bounds

The light-grey curves display reconstructed $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(2)}(\mathbb{R})[\{1, 5\}]$.

- * Centrality-parameter curve

The yellow curve displays reconstructed $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(2)}(\mathbb{R})[3]$.

²⁴For details on the reconstruction, refer to [19]

²⁵For each $j \in \mathbb{N}_{\leq J_{EPC}}$ and $k \in \mathbb{N}_{<5}$: $N | E_{jh} = 10^3$.

²⁶This code has parameter initialization that has been specified in the simulation setup discussed in [25].

²⁷Details of the lowpass filtering are discussed in Section B.5.

For details of the reconstruction, see the discussion following present list.

- *Row 4: Spectrogram*
Computed using the same methods as described in [19], the plots each show one power spectrum per column.
- *Row 5: Dynamical-stability diagnostics*
In this manuscript, $K_{PRT} = 4$ based on the diagnostic plots of [19] that show for *in vivo* data how four stereotypical broadband demodulates explain much of the periodicity in η and $\mathcal{G}_X^{(RES)}$. For $h \in \mathbb{N}_{<H_j}$, the four trendlines display all of the \bar{f}_{jk} -entries for all (E_{jh}, B_k) -combinations. The four coloured, piecewise, horizontal lines display \bar{f} .

Some important points are here detailed regarding that quantile-curve reconstruction for Row 3 which was mentioned in the above list. In effect, it has been assumed that $X^{(RES)}$ is the output of an SDE having innovation driver process, $X^{(INP)}$, whose FDD has the following specification: the K_N eigencoefficient spectra are jointly spherical to the extent of belonging to the Andrews class - itself, introduced in [18]²⁸ (here, $U_{DST} = 5$). Once having selected the innovation distribution, the methods from Section B.7.2 were employed to carry out the reconstruction.

For Row 3 plots, undercoverage bias in Θ -simulations is significant: the innovations process is dictated by Θ ; and with $U_{DST} = 5$, a small judgment sample has been drawn from the large population of probability-distribution families. Moreover, each sampling-unit distribution on the list frame cannot be a mixture of other list-frame distributions²⁹: if the first innovations time element is Gaussian with given parameter set, the rest of the time elements have distributions belonging to the Gaussian family (the second time element cannot be Gumbel-distributed).

For each of the two *in silico* source strata (the Figure 1 plot columns), it took 2 h³⁰ to execute per E_{jh} : an R code performing the following computations: filtering; generation of the Figure 1 plots; and other basic diagnostic multitaper analyses like that in [18] for the authors to check validity of Gaussian-eigencoefficient assumptions³¹.

4.2.2 The Quantile Diagnostics: An Alternative to the Spectrogram

Inspecting Figure 1 Rows 2 to 3: remark how across E_{RCD} the \mathbf{q}_θ -curves explain features like TRW propagation frequency. This section discusses why it requires a minimum of effort to validate the TRW assumption in the Biophysics model. During E_4 , the \mathbf{q}_θ -curves consistently track x-periodicity: indicating TRW-periodicity, since MEA-voltage consistently follows Type III dynamics.

Row 1

As expected for two different simulation models whose distinct biophysical sources have been designed to produce similar LFP-response: the Row 1 plots have similar x-

²⁸More on this distributional behaviour is discussed in Appendix B.3.2. See Definition E.3 regarding the Andrews class.

²⁹I.e., elements from the large population.

³⁰1.5-2.5 h, the median being 2 h (MEA-electrodes of indices 1-9 from the simulation data - the Electrode 7 time omitted in the ictal-wavefront calculation due to an interruption and subsequent run restart on data from the remaining MEA-electrodes).

³¹More on the topic of these diagnostic analyses (e.g., eigencoefficient sphericity and propriety tests, and frequency-uncertainty assessments) is provided in [18].

Figure 1: Novel diagnostic plots for *in silico* data reveal in the time domain both: the extent to which cortical, somatic-potential TRW's plausibly explain LFP-periodicity; and in which of the E_j these candidate TRW-sources occur. Left and right columns respectively correspond to the ictal-core and ictal-wavefront source strata. Vertical black bars demarcate the E_{jh} . Rows: 1 - x ; 2 - $\mathbf{q}_\theta(\mathbb{R})[\{1, 3\}]$ (grey), $\mathbf{q}_\theta(\mathbb{R})[2]$ (black); 3 - $\mathbf{q}_\theta(\mathbb{R})[k]$ for $k \in \{4, 8\}$ (light grey), $k \in \{5, 7\}$ (dark grey), and $k = 6$ (yellow) - all overlaid with x (black); 4 - spectrogram (dynamic spectral power); 5 - the $\{\bar{f}_{jk}\}_{k=1}^4$ (the 4 curves), and \bar{f} (the 12 horizontal lines).

traces³². These LFP-traces evolve over E_{RCD} in a manner that is detailed in Table 2. Remark that this table contains identified j and E_j ; justification is provided in the “Evidence” column. During times of high activity, it does seem from the plots that the periodic LFP-peaks manifest cyclostationarity; the activity fluctuations are temporally coherent.

Table 2: Observations of MEA-voltage dynamics in the top two Figure 1 plots. The “Left” and “Right” subheadings under the E_j column specify which of the two columns is under consideration from the figure.

j	E_j (s)		Epoch Type	Evidence
	Left	Right		
1	[0, 50]	[0, 100]	II	Unstructured noise.
2	{50}	{100}	I	Tall-standing peak.
3	[50, 75]	[100, 125]	II	Noise of minimal structure.
4	[75, 100]	[125, 200]	III	Periodic discharge troughs.
5	[100, 180]		II	Unstructured noise.

Row 2

For the left plot, compare the η -curve (black $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(1)}(\mathbb{R})[2]$ -trace) with the corresponding Row 1 LFP-curve (\mathbf{x} -trace). Notice in Row 2 how the ~ 10 mV-amplitudes of η -peaks during E_4 are not as accentuated from < 5 mV η -amplitudes during the other E_j as is the case in Row 1 for \mathbf{x} -amplitudes during these two epochs (~ 15 mV vs. 5 mV). The misfit arises from the Fourier uncertainty principle that necessitates inclusion of many high-frequency eigenmodes in η during times of sharpest $E_\theta \circ X$ fluctuation. Including the grey one-sigma curves makes a big difference during [75, 90] s; with the ~ 5 mV η -amplitudes nobably falling short of LFP-magnitudes. Whilst the left Row 2 plot suggests the Gaussian cyclostationary-APR model being accurate for \mathbf{x} under the ictal-core hypothesis: the right Row 2 plot for the ictal-wavefront simulation yields less impressive results because the one-sigma $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(1)}(\mathbb{R})[\{1, 3\}]$ -traces cannot explain the $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(1)}(\mathbb{R})[2]$ bias as an η -estimator.

Row 3

As expected: time-domain modeling accounts for those 5 mV η -deficits seen Row 2. Right plot: notice Row 3 how the $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(2)}(\mathbb{R})[3]$ -trace (yellow) better fits the \mathbf{x} -trace (black) than the Row 2 $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(1)}(\mathbb{R})[2]$ -trace (black): a near magnitude overlap between the \mathbf{x} and $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(2)}(\mathbb{R})[3]$ -traces. Including both pairs of inner (dark-grey, $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(2)}(\mathbb{R})[\{2, 4\}]$ -traces) and outer (light-grey, $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(2)}(\mathbb{R})[\{1, 5\}]$ -traces) one-sigma curves: both Row 2 plots reveal that cyclostationary modeling can be conservative accounting for innovation distributions as ill-behaved as those belonging to the Student family (left plot, during E_4 : excessive width of $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(2)}(\mathbb{R})[\{2, 4\}]$ -traces about the \mathbf{x} -trace > 5 mV in error).

Despite the $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(2)}$ -bounds being conservative, the quantile diagnostics remain invaluable for model-uncertainty analysis. Whilst in right plot the $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(2)}(\mathbb{R})[3]$ -trace does better than the Row 2 $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(1)}(\mathbb{R})[2]$ -trace to explain the E_4 \mathbf{x} -periodicity: the $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(2)}(\mathbb{R})[\{2, 4\}]$ -traces reflect the level of variation between seizures across the survey strata. These $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(2)}(\mathbb{R})[\{2, 4\}]$ -

³²The amplitude scales are similar. The Row 1 plots have been included with differing plotting scales is to ensure that Row 2 plots can be directly compared with Row 1 plots upon inclusion of the \mathbf{q}_θ -curves.

traces underestimate E_4 LFP *viz.*, the x -trace (~ 5 mV in the early $E_{4,h}$), but recall how periodic modeling of a nonlinear signal³³ is bound to produce these biasing effects: it was anticipated that the main feature to take away from the \mathbf{q}_θ -curves is the rate of TRW-peaks. Indeed, it is impressive how in both Row 3 plots the $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(2)}(\mathbb{R})[3]$ -trace so accurately fits x -amplitude.

Row 4

For blowups of the left and right spectrogram plots, respectively refer to the top-right plot of each of Figures 2 and 3. The quantile plots are easier to interpret than the spectrogram. During E_4 , little can be inferred from the spectrogram other than the presence of dominant low-frequency oscillations (the pronounced spectral peaks, manifesting as a sequence of regularly-spaced, horizontal white strips³⁴).

Row 5

The average-frequency diagnostics do well to demarcate the E_j : high-frequency oscillations contributing less during E_4 than in the other E_j (an abrupt disappearance of high-frequency eigenmodes manifesting as missing $\bar{\mathbf{f}}$ -entries). In addition, remark how the eigenfrequencies in B_k tend to evenly span that support; the $\bar{\mathbf{f}}[\mathbb{N}_{\leq J_{EPC}}, k]$ -curve lying centrally in B_k .

4.2.3 Data-based Motivation of the Novel Diagnostics

This section presents results from the Section 3.3.3 quality-assessment procedure. Reason suggests that the cyclic-spectrum statistical inference is reasonable despite its reliance on statistics suffering from error propagation.

Justifying the eigenfrequency diagnostics

Figure 2 displays diagnostic plots that between them provide an overview of LFP-periodicity. Top plots in Figures 2 A) and B) respectively magnify plots from Rows 1 and 4 down the left Figure 1 plot column. Both these two top plots are included to assist visualization of the lower plots in Figures 2 A) and B). Accompanying these two bottom plots, Tables 3 and 4 detail the plotted features: describing those features introduced Section 3.3.3 which these plot elements represent.

First motivation Start with the bottom Figure 2 A) plot: a diagnostic plot of E_{jh} -indexed η spectral harmonic coefficients (black clocks) and ν cepstral harmonic coefficients (red clocks). Beyond 100 s, the black-clock medians³⁵ align near 0 Hz: just at a time where one sees the TRW-stereotyped Turing/Hopf periodicity in the top Figure 2 A) x -trace plot. Extending outward from each of these medians is a pair of solid, vertical lines containing the respective $\mathcal{F}_{4,h}^{(\eta)}$ interquartile intervals³⁶: these vertical lines merely accentuating the level of overlap between the $B_\eta|E_{jh}$, and justifying the choice of stratified-average metrics because of the clear identification of a steady state.

Second motivation Why choose the eigenfrequency as the population characteristic of interest, and not the phase instead? Often in dynamical systems: harmonic phase is linearly dependent on eigenfrequency; the temporally-dependent phase term and the eigenfre-

³³I.e., extracting a demodulate (a.k.a. an oscillation) that behaves more nearly like a sinusoid.

³⁴Left plot - -40 dB; right plot - 50 dB) in $[0, 20]$ Hz.

³⁵I.e., $\mathbf{f}_j^{(MED)}$ -entries.

³⁶I.e., $\mathbf{f}_j^{(QRT)}$ -entries.

Figure 2: The most coherent periodicity is of the η kind during E_4 as specified in Table 2; yet, the ν -periodicity does remain statistically significant. The X eigenco-efficient spectra exhibit both propriety and joint sphericity. **A) *Top* - the x-trace; *bottom* - spectrogram of boxplots for both η spectral (black) and ν cepstral (red) phasor distributions (see Table 3 for specifications). **B)** *Top* - power spectrogram; *bottom* - spectrogram of PC-plots for joint propriety/sphericity (between each pair of delineating vertical epoch lines, the horizontal axis spans $[0, 1]$; see Table 4 for specifications).**

quency are interchangeable; and neuroscientists plot the full phase (sum of the temporally-dependent and stationary-intercept terms)³⁷. It so happens that $\mathcal{A}_{jh}^{(\eta)}$ is too variable, hence the choice of instead using the more stable $\mathcal{F}_{jh}^{(\eta)}$. The bold arc intersecting the clock handle spans angles contained inside the $\mathcal{A}_{jh}^{(\eta)}$ interquartile interval³⁸. Across the E_{4h} , there is no conspicuous alignment of these arcs or median directions; therefore, phase synchronization arises from the temporally-dependent phase term. Moreover, features of the $\mathcal{F}_{jh}^{(\eta)}$ -distribution are suitable dynamic-stability diagnostics.

Third motivation Why use the eigenfrequencies alone as dynamic-stability diagnostics, when the cyclic frequencies also play an important role in LFP-modeling? The red clocks are precisely the same as the black clocks, just now for the ν cepstral eigenmodes. Between them, the red clocks share less in common than do the black clocks. Whilst the red clocks appear consistently across epochs, the bottom Figure 2 A) plot shows their relative SNR fluctuating sporadically across the E_{jh} . As such, the cyclic frequencies serve more to explain LFP-variability than to identify the E_j .

Assessing error propagation

For each E_{jh} , the bottom Figure 2 B) plot displays diagnostics explaining the relative propriety/sphericity of eigenco-efficient spectra. Inside of E_{jh} , the bottom Figure 2 B) plot shows PC-axes drawn out one-sigma either direction from $\bar{\mathbf{F}}_{jh}^{(JNT)}$. As discussed in [19], PC-axes that are more nearly vertical - precisely what the plot depicts - indicate propriety

³⁷E.g., [51] and its accompanying references.

³⁸Recall the $\mathcal{A}_{jh}^{(\eta)}$ specification in Equation 14.

Table 3: Description of features in the lower Figure 2 A) plot that displays a boxplot spectrogram. In the figure, those mathematical objects from this table are respectively are plotted as black and red which are denoted using the **f**- and **q**-symbols.

Object	Start	End	Plot feature
Nyquist bound	$\inf E_{RCD}$	$\sup E_{RCD}$	Horizontals
$\{z \in \mathbb{C} : z = 1\}$	0 rad	2π rad	Clock rim
Real axis	$z = -1$	$z = 1$	Faint, solid horizontal
$\mathbf{f}_j^{(MED)}, \mathbf{q}_j^{(MED)}$	[h]		Clock centre
$\mathbf{f}_j^{(QRT)}, \mathbf{q}_j^{(QRT)}$	[h, 1]	[h, 2]	Bold, solid vertical
$\mathbf{f}_j^{(MMB)}, \mathbf{q}_j^{(MMB)}$	[h, 1]	[h, 2]	Dotted vertical
$\phi_j^{(MED)}, \varphi_j^{(MED)}$	[h]		Arrow along the clock handle
$\phi_j^{(QRT)}, \varphi_j^{(QRT)}$	[h, 1]	[h, 2]	Bold, solid arc (clock rim)
$\phi_j^{(MMB)}, \varphi_j^{(MMB)}$	[h, 1]	[h, 2]	Faint, solid arc (clock rim)
$\mathcal{T}_{jh}^{(\eta)}, \mathcal{T}_{jh}^{(v)}$	$\min \mathcal{T}_{jh}^{(\#)}$	$\max \mathcal{T}_{jh}^{(\#)}$	Heat bar

being stronger than sphericity. Most of the $\bar{\mathbf{F}}_{jh}^{(JNT)}$ lie below 0.8 on the vertical $F^{(IMP)}$ axis - suggesting propriety; and left of the midway mark of an E_{jh} interval - suggesting sphericity.

Ictal-wavefront TRW-source

Given that the ictal-wavefront simulation has been parameterized so that the resulting dynamics specifically mimic Turing/Hopf behaviour, it comes as no surprise that the diagnostic Figure 3 plots bare resemblance to those in Figure 2. Under the hypothesis of an ictal-wavefront source, it remains true that the eigencoeficient spectra exhibit propriety and joint sphericity.

Table 4: Descriptions of the features in the lower boxplot spectrogram of Figure 2 B).

Object	Start	End	Plot feature
$F^{(IMP)} = 0.5$	Record start	Record end	Black horizontal
$\bar{\mathbf{F}}_{jh}^{(JNT)} \rightarrow \bar{\mathbf{F}}_{j,h+1}^{(JNT)}$	$\bar{\mathbf{F}}_{jh}^{(JNT)}$	$\bar{\mathbf{F}}_{j,h+1}^{(JNT)}$	Connector line
PC_2^1	$\bar{\mathbf{F}}_{jh}^{(JNT)} - \mathbf{p}_{jh,2}^{(JNT)}$	$\bar{\mathbf{F}}_{jh}^{(JNT)} + \mathbf{p}_{jh,2}^{(JNT)}$	Tilted line inside E_{jh}
$\left\ \mathbf{p}_{jh,2}^{(JNT)} \right\ _2$	$\min \mathcal{P}_1^{(JNT)}$	$\max \mathcal{P}_1^{(JNT)}$	Heat bar

Figure 3: Changing from an ictal-core to an ictal-wavefront source does not greatly affect model uncertainty. Same as Figure 2, except now for a simulated ictal-wavefront source.

4.3 Clinical Data

Analogous to Figure 1: Figure 4 summarizes a diagnostic analysis for both of the *in vivo* source strata discussed in Section 2.1³⁹. For each of these source strata, it takes < 2 h⁴⁰ to execture an R code performing the same tasks as previously mentioned for the *in silico*

³⁹For the Patient C5 and MG49 source strata, the respective $N | E_{jh}$ -ranges are $N | E_{jh} \in \mathbb{N}_{[594,603]}$ and $N | E_{jh} \in \mathbb{N}_{[756,765]}$ (with the exception of E_{j,H_j} , itself containing 10^3 record points).

⁴⁰1.25-2 h for the Patient C5 stratum, the median being 1.5 h (MEA-electrodes of indices belonging to $\{20,40,47,56,58,87,92\}$); and 1.5-2 h for the Patient MG49 stratum, the median being 1.9 h (MEA-electrodes of indices belonging to $\{1,20,40,47,56,58,89,92,96\}$).

source strata.

Figure 4: The same way as in Figure 1, *in vivo* seizure data evince cortical, somatic-potential TRW's: The same diagnostics as in Figure 1, except that now the left and right columns respectively correspond to the Patient C5 and Patient MG49 source strata.

Cyclostationary time-series modeling is just as important to understand TRW-dynamics for the *in vivo* source strata as it is for the *in silico* source strata. In both Figure 4 Row 1 plots, α -periodicity near record centre⁴¹ reveals that the state of the system falls somewhere in between Types II and III. Under the SDE-model of [25], medium-stability dynamics

⁴¹Left plot - 16.9 min + [30, 50] s, right plot - 12 min + [30, 50] s.

in this E_j indicates that the dynamical system is entering a spatially-organized state⁴². During these times of intermediate stability, $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(1)}(\mathbb{R})[2]$ has low bias as an η -estimator: the black curves of each Row 2 plot track the respective data curves of the Row 1 plots. In addition, state variance tends to be low⁴³. Inspecting both Row 4 spectrograms, remark how said excellent fit arises because medium-stability X -dynamics are synonymous with APR-periodicity - especially in the left spectrogram plot, where evenly-spaced $[0, 60]$ Hz spectral peaks produce a zebra pattern in $16.9 \text{ min} + [30, 60]$ s. This intermediate stability has the effect of stabilizing the Row 5 $\bar{\mathbf{f}}$ -curves, especially in B_1 and B_2 .

In addition to aforementioned durations of good fit, there are times in E_{RCD} also where η -modeling is insufficient to explain X -periodicity. Just as for the *in silico* source strata discussed Section 4.2.2, $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(1)}(\mathbb{R})[2]$ -traces in both Row 2 plots achieve the weakest fits during the E_{jh} late seizure (i.e., Type III dynamics). Another parallel with the *in silico* strata: during times of Type III periodicity late seizure, both Row 3 plots reveal the yellow $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(2)}(\mathbb{R})[3]$ -trace tracking the black \mathbf{x} -trace.

Both Figure 4 Row 1 plots evince TRW's. However, only exploring the Row 2 plots means relying on X -reconstruction that relies on inferred parameters from the frequency domain rather than the time domain. This ensures significant error propagation because of the FFT-operation and the smoothing effects that come with it. As such, the novel diagnostics for the four source strata all show the expected outcome that Row 3 quantile curves should accompany the Row 2 and Row 4 plots. With the novel quantile curves in Rows 2-3 together suggesting the presence of TRW's, it makes sense to finding resection sites using medical-imaging techniques: SOZ-localization via a COM calculation is justified, so long as no restricting assumption is made about there being but a single focal TRW.

5. Conclusions and Future Directions

Neuroscientists ought scrutinize the established assumption that a sparse cosine-series signal element accurately explains those TRW's which are induced by the generative Biophysics. When this assumption is invalid: a wavepacket model has limited potential for COM-localization purposes; and simulation benchmarking like that in [40] may well be more likely to identify lesion sites that achieve appreciable success rate in resection surgery.

In the modeling steps of this manuscript, Appendix C specifies an assumption that X is linearly related to the somatic local spike firing rate⁴⁴. Whilst linearity assumptions are ubiquitous in physical modeling and may well prove useful approximations where concerns justification for robust statistical diagnostics: said assumption requires more rigorous proof from Physics. Future work must produce an electrodynamical model accounting for the linearity assumption. To this end, it is here proposed to take a snapshot of the TRW's. In this snapshot, several static TRW-wavefronts are present in cortex: a number of wavefronts per TRW-source (one TRW for a focal source, and an arbitrary number of TRW's for an ictal-wavefront source). Thus, each TRW-source produces its own concentric, static-charge distribution inside a permeable, water-dominated medium: a problem with known solution if one uses the differential-equation theory of [9].

⁴²I.e., those Turing dynamics which precede the high-stability epochs of Turing/Hopf-dynamics that have the additional temporal Hopf stability. Refer to Appendix C for more details regarding the generative biophysical model of [47]: itself, employed by [25] to explain TLE.

⁴³Grey curves in Row 2 bound a 2-sigma region that is especially narrow.

⁴⁴Viz., Equation 85.

6. Acknowledgments

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A. Manuscript Notation

Acronyms

APR almost-periodic. 2, 5, 8, 13, 16, 22, 30, 31, 37, 38, 41, 50–52

ARIMA autoregressive, integrated moving average. 41, 49, 56

BIN binomial-expansion. 30, 55

C Columbia University. 4

COM centre of mass. 4, 5, 9, 13, 22

CYC cyclic-frequency. 49

DST distribution. 7, 32

EPC epochs. 6, 30

FDD finite-dimensional distribution. 6–8, 11, 12, 14, 34, 37–39, 41, 43, 48, 49, 53

FFT fast-Fourier-transform. 9–12, 22, 30, 37, 43, 46, 49

HII high indices. 39

IMP impropriety. 12, 30

INP input. 36, 45, 53

JNT joint. 12

LAT linear APR time-variant. 6, 30, 36, 39, 41, 45, 46, 53

LFP local field potential. 2, 4–7, 13–18, 32, 38, 42, 51

LIN linear. 45, 52

LNI linear NSS input. 45

LNN linear-noise. 45

LNR linear-residual. 45

LNW linear NSS whitened. 45

LOI low indices. 39

LTI linear time-invariant. 51

MAX maximum. 51

MEA microelectrode array. 4–6, 9–11, 13, 14, 16, 20, 48, 51

MED median. 10

MG MGH. 4

MGH Massachusetts General Hospital. 4, 5

MMB min/max bounds. 10

MOD modulators. 30, 53

MSARIMA multiple SARIMA. 30, 41, 42, 48, 50, 51

MSR multiple SARIMA. 41

NLI nonlinear NSS input. 45

NLN nonlinear-noise. 45

NLR nonlinear-residual. 45

NLW nonlinear NSS whitened. 45

NON nonlinear. 45, 52

NRM normalization. 48

NSE noise. 30, 36, 45

NSS narrow-sense stationary. 42, 43, 48, 50

NSW whitened noise. 36, 45

OFS offset. 31, 53

PC principal-component. 12, 18

PIT probability integral transform. 11, 12, 30

PRT partition. 6, 30

QRT quartiles. 10

RCD record. 6, 30

RES residual. 7, 45

SARIMA seasonal ARIMA. 41, 42

SDE stochastic differential equation. 5, 10, 12–14, 21

SGN signal. 32, 36

SNR signal-to-noise ratio. 2, 5, 6, 18, 31, 35–37, 39, 42, 43

SOZ seizure-onset zone. 4, 22

SPH sphericity. 12, 30

STD standardized. 51

TLE temporal-lobe epilepsy. 4, 11, 12, 22

TML timelimited. 30, 43

TRD trend. 7, 31

TRW traveling wave. 4–6, 12–15, 17, 19, 21, 22, 38

Mathematical Notation: Manuscript-specific

\mathcal{A}_j	All \mathcal{A}_1 -elements are equal to \emptyset , and the u 'th \mathcal{A}_2 -element is equal to $\{0, u\}$.
B	The backshift operator.
B_k, K_{PRT}	B_k is the k 'th of K_{PRT} partition (PRT) bands.
η_m	The m 'th η signal element.
\mathcal{C}_S	The APR-component class given S the spectral support.
$\mathcal{C}(t; A)$	Contains cosine functions: each evaluated at time t ; and the m 'th element equal to zero unless its normalized frequency lies in A .
$D^{S\#}, D^K,$ $H_D^{(\#)}$	Here, $D^{S\#}$ is a composition of iterated-differentiation operators, the K 'th of which is D^K ($D^K \Leftrightarrow H_D^K$, with D^K the K 'th-order iterated-differentiation operator).
$\Delta_S, \check{\Delta}_S$	MSARIMA system function, and its discrete-time estimate.
E_{NSE}, A_{NSE}	E_{NSE} is an index set on the positive integers used to build the set, A_{NSE} , of noise (NSE) cyclic-frequency indices that is symmetric about the origin.
$E_{RCD}, E_j,$ $J_{EPC} E_{jh}, H_j$	The record (RCD) window; its j 'th of J_{EPC} dynamics epochs (EPC); and the h 'th of $H_j E_j$ micro-epochs.
$f_m, \omega_m, M_N,$ $\Delta_N f$	The m 'th of M_N FFT-frequencies (ω_m the associated angular frequency); the grid spacing being $\Delta_N f$.
$\mathcal{F}_{jh}^{(\#)}, \mathcal{A}_{jh}^{(\#)}$	$\mathcal{F}_{jh}^{(\#)}$ is a collection of FFT-frequencies estimating the normalized eigenfrequencies of that signal element which is specified by the superscript (η or ν). Analogous to $\mathcal{F}_{jh}^{(\#)}$, the $\mathcal{A}_{jh}^{(\#)}$ -class contains in place of f_m : the principal argument of the η_m -amplitude.
$F_{jh}^{(SPH)}(f),$ $\mathbf{F}_{jh}^{(SPH)},$ $F_{jh}^{(IMP)}(f),$ $\mathbf{F}_{jh}^{(IMP)}$ $\bar{F}_{jh}^{(SPH)},$ $\bar{\mathbf{F}}_{jh}^{(SPH)},$ $\bar{F}_{jh}^{(IMP)},$ $\bar{\mathbf{F}}_{jh}^{(IMP)}$	For E_{jh} : $F_{jh}^{(SPH)}(f)$ and $F_{jh}^{(IMP)}(f)$ are the frequency- f PIT's respectively for the test statistics of the probability integral transform (PIT) and sphericity (SPH) impropriety (IMP) tests. A coincidence histogram, $\mathbf{N}_{jh}^{(JNT)}$, has x-axis indexed on $\mathbf{F}_{jh}^{(SPH)}$ and $\mathbf{F}_{jh}^{(IMP)}$. Respectively contain the averages over entries of the vectors, $\mathbf{F}_{jh}^{(SPH)}$ and $\mathbf{F}_{jh}^{(IMP)}$.
$\mathcal{G}_K^{(BIN)}(z, f),$ $\mathcal{H}_A^{(BIN)}(z; \xi)$	$\mathcal{G}_k^{(BIN)}(z; f)$ is a sequence of binomial-expansion (BIN) functions associated with the summand in the binomial expansion of $(z + f^2)^K$. A function of $\mathcal{G}_u^{(BIN)}(z; f)$: the u 'th element of the $\mathcal{H}_A^{(BIN)}(z; \xi)$ -sequence (the u 'th \mathcal{A} -element denoted A_u) sets out up front the A_u -indexed partial sum from the that binomial expansion which is governed by $\mathcal{G}_u^{(BIN)}(z; f)$.
$g_m^{(TML)}$	B_{TML} -timelimited (TML) cosine-series signal (B_{TML} the spectral support).
$\mathcal{G}^{(MOD)}, h_m, h$	The class of modulators (MOD) for an LAT-process, with the m 'th time-variant filter function denoted h_m ($h = h_0$).

$\mathcal{G}_X^{(\#)}, A_{\#}, \gamma_X^{(\#)}$	The class of fixed-lag $\Theta = \theta$ -conditioned $X^{(\#)}$ autocorrelation functions: the corresponding class of cyclic-frequency indices denotes $A_{\#}$, and the functions denoted as $\gamma_X^{(\#)}$.
$\mathcal{G}_X^{(NSE)}(\tau), \gamma_{X,m}^{(NSE)}, \gamma_{Z,m}^{(OFS)}, \gamma_Z^{(NSE)}, Z^{(NSE)}, H, Z^{(INP)}$	Contains the X rotational cyclic autocorrelation functions (the m 'th denoted as $\gamma_{X,m}^{(NSE)}$) - each evaluated at lag, τ . The $\gamma_{Z,m}^{(OFS)}$ offset (OFS) function associated with $\gamma_Z^{(NSE)}$ the rotational autocorrelation function of the Fourier-transform process, $Z^{(NSE)}$, of $X^{(NSE)}$. Meanwhile, $Z^{(NSE)}$ is related to the $X^{(INP)}$ Fourier-transform process, $Z^{(INP)}$, within a transfer function, H .
k_K^*	Epoch-specification signal.
$\check{L}_S(f)$	The frequency- f element of the log-transform of $\check{\Delta}_S$ on a unit-circle f points of 2π round.
ν, ν_m	Low-SNR signal and its m 'th signal element.
$\mathcal{L}_{\#}$	Operator.
Ω, \mathcal{F}, P	Sample space; a sigma field in Ω ; and the probability measure on the measurable space, (Ω, P) .
$P_{\Theta}, P_{\theta}, p_{\theta}, \mathbf{p}_{\theta}$	Probability measures - respectively given Θ and given $\{\Theta = \theta\}$ - and associated density, p_{θ} , and U_{DST} -dimensional signal whose time- t element has j 'th entry being the time- t element of the u 'th distribution family.
$\mathbf{p}_{jh,1}^{(JNT)}, \mathbf{p}_{jh,2}^{(JNT)}, \mathcal{P}_1^{(JNT)}$	Respectively, $\mathbf{p}_{jh,1}^{(JNT)}$ and $\mathbf{p}_{jh,2}^{(JNT)}$ contain scaled versions of the first and second $\mathbf{N}_{jh}^{(JNT)}$ principal-component vectors. In addition, $\mathcal{P}_1^{(JNT)}$ contains the associated scales: themselves, the associated principal-component standard deviations.
$\phi_m(t)$	The time- t element of the m 'th phase signal.
ϕ_1, ϕ_{11}	Respectively, the AR(1) system function and associated coefficient.
$\varphi_1(f)$	The sequence over all ϕ_{11} of $\phi_1(f)$.
$\psi, g^{(TRD)}, \eta, B_{\eta}$	A signal element, Ψ , decomposed in trend (TRD) ($g^{(TRD)}$) and high-SNR (η, B_{η} spectral support) X signal elements.
Ψ, Ψ_j	Ψ_j is the j 'th element of Ψ the collection of expansion coefficients for a causal linear filter.
$\mathbf{Q}, p_X, \mathbf{q}_{\theta}, \mathbf{q}_{\theta}^{(j)}$	The 8D quantile signal, \mathbf{q}_{θ} , whose time- t element is specified by a two-block augmented vector: the blocks denoted $\mathbf{q}_{\theta}^{(1)}(t)$ and $\mathbf{q}_{\theta}^{(2)}(t)$, respectively time- t elements of 3D and 5D quantile signals that are specified by two distinct models. The quantile signal is specified by the random quantile matrix, \mathbf{Q} .
$Q_b^{(\#)}, V_b^{(\#)}, CV_{\theta}, \{V_{b,j}\}_{j=0}^1, \phi_b$	A version, $V_b^{(\#)}$ of b -type somatic potential (possibly normalized: with the $V_{b,j}$ APR-coefficients, and ϕ_b a corresponding dynamic phase): the potential related to $Q_b^{(\#)}$ some function of the local somatic-spike firing rate. In addition, CV_{θ} is the $\{\Theta = \theta\}$ -conditioned coefficient of variation.
$S_{\#}, \check{S}_{\#}$	an ordered set of cyclic-period indices. The estimating set, $\check{S}_{\#}$, is equal to $S_{\#}$ for odd $S_{\#}$ -elements and incremented for even $S_{\#}$ -elements.

$t, t_n, \Delta t$	The record time, t , and a specific t -value, t_n : itself, the n 'th $\Delta t\mathbb{Z}$ -element, and with Δt the sampling period.
$\mathcal{T}_{jh}^{(\#)}$	The multitaper harmonic F-statistic spectrum for a time series associated whose information is restricted to that in E_{jh} . The $\#$ superscript symbol is replaced by the mathematical symbol of the signal element of interest (i.e., η or ν).
$\Theta, \Theta_u, U_{DST}, \theta, \theta_u$	The \mathbb{R} -indexed $(U_{DST} + 2)$ -block augmented stochastic parameter process (Θ_u the u 'th block with the realization, θ_u), and its realization, θ , corresponding to that X -realization which coincides with $\{\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{x}\}$: U_{DST} the cardinality of the class of X probability-distribution (DST) families considered in the model-uncertainty analysis.
ν, B_ν	A cosine-series signal element (ν , spectral support B_ν) that is to the time series of log-transformed multitaper $X^{(RES)}$ spectral-power estimates what η is to \mathbf{x} .
W	Multitaper bandwidth parameter.
$X^{(\#)}, x^{(\#)}, \mathcal{X}^{(\#)}, \mathbf{X}^{(\#)}, \mathbf{x}^{(\#)}$	The univariate LFP-oscillation, $X^{(\#)}$; its Δt -discretization; the vectorized version of $\mathcal{X}^{(\#)}$ on $[0, t_{N-1}]$ (N the record size), and its realization, $\mathbf{x}^{(\#)}$ (the measured time series).
$x^{(SGN)}, s$	The mean X signal (SGN), containing the s -component that is a seasonal trend.
$Z^{(\#)}$	The integrated process of $X^{(\#)}$.
$z_m^{(\#)}$	The m 'th amplitude in a cosine-series expansion of the signal element, $x^{(\#)}$.

Mathematical Notation: Established

This manuscript adopts the following notation.

1. *Mathematics.*

- Sets.
 - \mathbb{N} contains the natural numbers.
 - \mathbb{R} contains the real numbers.
 - \mathbb{Z} contains the integers.
- Complex Analysis: Log is the principal logarithm.
- Delta functions.
 - δ is the Dirac delta function.
 - Given $j \in \mathbb{Z}$: $\delta_{j,\mathbb{Z}}$ is the Kronecker delta function.
- Set theory
 - \mathcal{B} is the Borel sigma field in $[0, 1]$ [2].
 - Given $B \subset A \subset \mathbb{R}$: the restriction, A_B , of A to B is given by [36]

$$A_B = A \cap B. \quad (16)$$

- Indicators. For $A \in \mathbb{R}^{45}$,
 - * χ_A is the indicator function on A ; and
 - * For $A \subset \mathbb{R}$, the indicator sequence, \mathcal{I}_A , is given by

$$\mathcal{I}_A = \{ \chi_A(u) \}_{u \in \mathbb{Z}_A}. \quad (17)$$

2. *Probability space.* All random variables in this manuscript are assigned to a single probability space, (Ω, \mathcal{F}, P) .

- Ω is the sample space.
- \mathcal{F} is a sigma field in Ω .
- P is the probability measure.

3. *Products:* Let $p \in \mathbb{N}_{>1}$.

- Signal elements⁴⁶
 - Continuous signal elements
For $\xi, \zeta \in L^2(A)$ with $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}$: $\langle \xi | \zeta \rangle_{L^2(A)}$ denotes the Hilbert inner product of ξ and $\chi_A \zeta$ ⁴⁷. In the convolution expression, ξ is that integrand-factor function which has been both translated and conjugated.

⁴⁵Notation from [36, 2].

⁴⁶Refer to Definition E.1 on signal elements.

⁴⁷The specific variation of the bra/ket notation of [4, 36] has been drawn from [9].

– Discrete signal elements

For $\xi, \zeta \in \ell^p(A)$ with $A \subseteq \mathbb{Z}$: $\langle \xi | \zeta \rangle_{\ell^2(A)}$ is the summation equivalent of $\langle \xi | \zeta \rangle_{L^2(A)}$ (when $A = \mathbb{R}$, write ℓ^p for $\ell^p(A)$ and denote by ℓ_p the associated ℓ^p -space).

– Write L^p and ℓ^p respectively for $L^p(A)|A = \mathbb{R}$ and $\ell^p(B)|B = \mathbb{Z}$ ⁴⁸.

– Vectors

For $\xi, \zeta \in \mathbb{R}^p$: $\langle \xi | \zeta \rangle$ is the dot product of the two vectors.

• Random variables

$L^\infty(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, P)$ is an equivalence class whose operator is the same as that for the class of essentially-bounded, measurable functions: excepting for the replacement of the L^p -norm operator by the p 'th absolute mean [36, 4].

4. *Conditional Probability* In Section 3, a stochastic process, X , is introduced. The X finite-dimensional distribution (FDD), is parameterized by Θ : itself, a vector-valued stochastic process. Consider $Y \in L^2(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, P)$.

• Probability measure

– μ_Θ is the Θ -conditioned X probability distribution, and is given by

$$\mu_\Theta(H) = P_\Theta[Y \in H]. \quad (18)$$

In Equation 18, P_Θ is the conditional-probability variable [2, 37]:

$$P_\Theta[Y \in H] = P[\{Y \in H\}|\Theta]. \quad (19)$$

– Denote by P_θ the $\{\Theta = \theta\}$ -conditioned X probability measure, and denote by μ_θ and the associated distribution.

• Random parameters

– Respectively denote by $E_\Theta[Y]$ and $\text{Var}_\Theta[Y]$ the abbreviations for $E[Y|\Theta]$ and $\text{Var}[Y|\Theta]$.

– Denote by E_θ and Var_θ respectively the $\{\Theta = \theta\}$ -conditioned expectation and variance operators [37].

⁴⁸Notation from [36, 2].

B. Theory and Methods

This section relies heavily on notation from Appendix A; upon reading of this section here present, the reader is encouraged to return frequently to that section.

B.1 Parameterization: The Switching Model

Recall the stochastic parameter process, Θ , from Section 3.2. For $t \in \mathbb{R}$, the t 'th state is given by

$$\{\Theta(t)\}^T = [\Theta_u(t)]_{u=1}^{U_{DST}+2} : \quad (20)$$

the first $U_{DST}+1$ blocks each a function of $\Theta_{U_{DST}+2}(t)$ that itself satisfies

$$P [\Theta_{U_{DST}+2}(t)[1] = k_{J_{EPC}}^*(t)] = 1. \quad (21)$$

and

$$P [\Theta_{U_{DST}+2}(t)[2] = k_{H_j}^*(t) : j = k_{J_{EPC}}^*(t)] = 1. \quad (22)$$

In Equations 21 and 22, k^* for $K \in \mathbb{N}$ is an epoch-specification signal given by

$$k_K^*(t) = \left\langle \mathbb{Z} \left| \mathcal{I}_{[1,K]} \left(\left\lfloor \frac{t}{\Delta t} \right\rfloor \right) \right\rangle_{\ell^2} (0). \quad (23)$$

When $u \in \mathbb{N}_{\leq U_{DST}}$: $\Theta_u(t)$ contains the parameters of the u 'th distribution family. In addition, $\Theta_{U_{DST}+1}(t)$ is a univariate switching variable that satisfies the following properties.

1. The range of $\Theta_{U_{DST}+1}(t)$ is $\mathbb{N}_{\leq U_{DST}}$.
2. The P_{θ} -density, p_{θ} , is specified according to the value of the switching variable:

$$p_{\theta} = \langle \delta \circ \theta_{U_{DST}+1}(t) \mid \mathbf{p}_{\theta}(t) \rangle_{\ell^2} (0). \quad (24)$$

In Equation 24, the terms are given as follows.

- θ_u is the Θ_u -realization.
- δ is a U_{DST} -dimensional block-indicator signal: indexed on $\mathbb{N}_{\leq U_{DST}}$; and given by
$$\delta(u)[j] = \delta_{j,u}. \quad (25)$$
- \mathbf{p}_{θ} is a U_{DST} -dimensional signal: indexed on \mathbb{R} ; and whose u 'th entry is the $\{\Theta = \theta\}$ -conditioned probability density function of the u 'th distribution family.

B.2 The Time-series Model

Appendix B.2.1 provides the full signal-plus-noise decomposition that gives rise to the presented decomposition of Section 3.2. Whilst Appendix B.2.2 details a high-SNR element of the signal part, the rigorous specifications on the noise part are more specialized to producing good time-domain diagnostics than containing assumptions that generalize to as broad as possible a class of stochastic processes. Therefore, the noise-component specifications are reserved to Appendix B.3 regarding diagnostic quantile curves.

B.2.1 A Signal-plus-noise Decomposition

The model specifications are inspired by the biophysical modeling held established by neuroscientists⁴⁹.

Assumption 5. The stochastic process, X , from Section 3 has a signal-plus-noise decomposition,

$$X = x^{(SGN)} + X^{(NSE)}, \quad (26)$$

where: $x^{(SGN)}$ is the mean signal (SGN) given by

$$x^{(SGN)} = \mathbf{E}_{\theta} \circ X; \quad (27)$$

and $X^{(NSE)}$ is the noise (NSE). Satisfying [4], the mean signal has the decomposition,

$$x^{(SGN)} = g^{(TRD)} + s, \quad (28)$$

where: $g^{(TRD)}$ is the trend term from Section 3; and s is a seasonal trend. The seasonal trend has the decomposition,

$$s = \eta + \nu, \quad (29)$$

where: η is the high-SNR, cosine-series signal element from Section 3; and the low-SNR signal, ν , is given by

$$\nu = \langle \mathcal{I}_{M_N B_\nu} | \nu \mathbb{Z} \rangle_{\ell^2}(0). \quad (30)$$

In Equation 30: the echo-period band, B_ν , satisfies

$$2M_N B_\nu \subseteq \left(1, \frac{M_N}{2} \right); \quad (31)$$

and ν_m is the m 'th low-SNR signal element.

Assumption 6. For \mathcal{L}_{NSE} a linear whitening operator, there exists a whitened noise (NSW), $X^{(NSW)}$, such that

$$X^{(NSW)} := \mathcal{L}_{NSE} X^{(NSE)} \quad (32)$$

and $X^{(NSW)}$ is LAT⁵⁰ in the following sense. The whitened noise is given by

$$X^{(NSW)} = \mathcal{L}_{LAT} X^{(INP)}, \quad (33)$$

where: \mathcal{L}_{NSE} is an LAT-filter operator; and $X^{(INP)}$ is cyclostationary input (INP). Denote by

$$S_{INP} \subset \mathbb{N} \cap \left(1, \frac{N}{2} \right) \quad (34)$$

the increasing set of $X^{(INP)}$ cyclic periods.

⁴⁹See Appendix C for justification.

⁵⁰Definition E.4 covers LAT-processes.

B.2.2 The High-SNR Signal

The high-SNR signal, η ⁵¹, has the decomposition,

$$\eta = \langle \mathcal{I}_{M_N B_\eta} | \eta \mathbb{Z} \rangle_{\ell^2}(0). \quad (35)$$

In Equation 35, B_η satisfies

$$2M_N B_\eta \subseteq \mathbb{Z}_{[0, M_N]}, \quad (36)$$

while the m 'th eigenmode, η_m , is given by

$$\eta_m(t) = 2 \left| z_m^{(\eta)} \right| \cos \circ \phi_m(t). \quad (37)$$

In Equation 37, the terms are given as follows.

- $z_m^{(\eta)} \in \mathbb{C}$ is the m 'th amplitude.
- The m 'th phase signal, ϕ_m , is given by

$$\phi_m(t) = \omega_m \frac{t}{\Delta t} + \text{Arg} \left(z_m^{(\eta)} \right). \quad (38)$$

In Equation 38, the terms are given as follows.

- The first term is the dynamic phase of η_m and the second term is the stationary phase of η_m .
- The m 'th angular frequency, ω_m , is given by $\omega_m = 2\pi f_m$, where the m 'th centred FFT-frequency, f_m , satisfies

$$2 \frac{f_m}{\Delta_N f} \in M_N \mathbb{Z}_{(-1,1]}. \quad (39)$$

In Equation 39, $\Delta_N f$ is the FFT grid spacing.

- Arg denotes the principal-argument operator from Complex Analysis.

B.3 The Diagnostic Curves

B.3.1 The Random Quantile Matrix

Recall the random quantile matrix, \mathbf{Q} , from Equation 10 in Section 3.3.1. The random matrix is itself given by $\mathbf{Q}^T = [\mathbf{Q}_1, \mathbf{Q}_2]$. For $k \in \{2, \frac{1}{3}\}$, the first block is given by

$$\mathbf{Q}_1[k, n] = \left\{ E_{\Theta} \pm (1 - \delta_{k,2}) \text{Var}_{\Theta}^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\} \circ \mathbf{X}[n]. \quad (40)$$

The \mathbf{Q}_1 -block is amenable to cyclostationary-APR modeling when the X -FDD is Gaussian because: for $k \in \{2, \frac{1}{3}\}$,

$$P_{\Theta} \left[\mathbf{Q}_1[k, n] = \eta(t_n) \pm (1 - \delta_{k,2}) \left| \gamma_X^{(RES)}(t_n, t_n) \right|^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] = 1. \quad (41)$$

In other words, Equation 41 presents the mean and error bars given $\{\Theta = \theta\}$.

⁵¹From Appendix B.2.

The second block is given by

$$\mathbf{Q}_2[k, n] = \begin{cases} \inf_{\sup} \{ \inf, \sup \} \arg \mu_{\Theta}^{(RES)}(1 - p_X)[n] & k = \frac{1}{2}, \frac{4}{5} \\ \Theta_{U_{DST+1}(t_n) \in L^\infty(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, P)} & \\ \text{ave} \{ \mathbf{Q}_2[n, j] \}_{j \in \{1, 5\}} & k = 3. \end{cases} \quad (42)$$

In Equation 42, the N -dimensional stochastic process, $\arg \mu_{\Theta}^{(RES)}$ is indexed on $[0, 1]$; and given by

$$P_{\theta} \left[X^{(RES)}(t_n) \in \arg \mu_{\Theta}^{(RES)}(\xi)[n] \right] = \xi \quad (43)$$

uniformly $\xi \in [0, 1]$ and $n \in \mathbb{Z}_{[0, N]}$. In Equation 43, one interprets the $\arg \mu_{\Theta}^{(RES)}(\xi)[n]$ as the argument function for the random measure, $\mu_{\Theta}^{(RES)}(\mathcal{B})[n]$: the randomness exclusively arising from Θ . With that specification in place, that makes $\arg \mu_{\Theta}^{(RES)}(\xi)[n]$ a random set, precisely in the notation of [16] that uses this convenient notation to explain the ordering of entries in a random vector for the purposes of survey sampling.

The following two points explain how \mathbf{Q}_2 explains model uncertainty.

1. For $k = \frac{1}{2}, \frac{4}{5}$,

$$\mathbf{q}_{\theta}(t_n)[k] = \inf_{\sup} \{ \inf, \sup \} H_n. \quad (44)$$

$\Theta_{U_{DST+1}(t_n) \in \mathbb{N} \leq U_{DST}}$

In Equation 44, H_n is given by

$$H_n = \arg \mu_{\theta}^{(RES)}(1 - p_X)[n], \quad (45)$$

such that

$$P_{\theta} \left[X^{(RES)}(t_n) \in H_n \right] = 1 - p_X. \quad (46)$$

2. In Equation 44, the first operator on H_n accounts for uncertainty under FDD-hypothesis; and the second operator in the composition accounts for uncertainty in Θ (i.e., the model uncertainty)⁵².

In this manuscript, further specifications are imposed on \mathbf{Q}_1 and \mathbf{Q}_2 to ensure straightforward, time-efficient computations: enabling neuroscientists with large-scale complex surveys to quickly generate the numerous diagnostic plots they wish to scan for that stereotyped LFP-periodicity which is indicative of TRW's. Appendix B.3.2 describes in detail these specifications.

B.3.2 The Quantile Curves: Model Assumptions

Recall the random quantile matrix, \mathbf{Q} , from Section B.3.1. Those specifications on this matrix placed in this section refer to the components in the time-series model presented Appendix B.2.

Top block

Recall from the discussion around Equation 41 how \mathbf{Q}_1 is amenable to cyclostationary-APR modeling when the X -FDD is Gaussian. The following assumption makes explicit that comment.

⁵²The \mathbf{Q}_2 -specification is typical in statistical modeling with physical applications [21].

Assumption 7. The noise, $X^{(NSE)}$, is LAT. That is: $g^{(TRD)}$ ⁵³ vanishes; and \mathcal{L}_{NSE} is the Dirac delta functional⁵⁴:

$$\mathcal{L}_{NSE} g = \langle \delta | g \rangle_{L^2}, \quad (47)$$

for $g \in L^2$. In addition, $X^{(INP)}$ is Gaussian.

Bottom block

Recall from Appendix B.1 that Θ is constructed using $(U_{DST} + 2)$ vector-valued stochastic processes, the u 'th of which is denoted Θ_u . Two assumptions are made for \mathbf{Q}_2 . For $S \subset \mathbb{N}$ increasing and containing unique elements, define D^S a composition of iterated differential operators: the K 'th being D^K . The first of these $|S|$ derivatives is of lowest order and the last is of highest order⁵⁵.

Construct S_{NSE} : called the noise index set, and having the decomposition,

$$S_{NSE} = S_d \cup S_{INP}, \quad (48)$$

with $S_d = \{1\}_{j=1}^d$ ⁵⁶. Partition S_{INP} as

$$S_{INP} = S_{LOI} \cup S_{HII}, \quad (49)$$

where S_{LOI} and S_{HII} respectively denote sets of low indices (LOI) and high indices (HII). The following assumption is essential for the FDD-inference and simulation used for the $\mathbf{q}_{\theta^{(2)}}$ -reconstructions of this manuscript.

Assumption 8. Components in the time-series model from Appendix B.2 satisfy the following conditions.

- The residual process, $X^{(RES)}$, satisfies the following properties.
 - Its mean signal satisfies

$$\mathbb{E}_{\theta} \circ X^{(RES)} = \nu + g^{(TRD)}. \quad (50)$$

- The residual process, $X^{(RES)}$, is related to $X^{(INP)}$ through the expression,

$$X^{(INP)} = \mathcal{L}_{NSE} X^{(RES)}. \quad (51)$$

- The m 'th low-SNR signal element, ν_m has identical functional form to η_m , bar a potential amplitude difference.
- The input, $X^{(INP)}$, is an innovation process belonging to the Andrews class⁵⁷.
- Definition E.2 on linear/nonlinear decomposition models⁵⁸ specifies a model process, Ξ : its linear and nonlinear components respectively denoted $\Xi^{(LIN)}$ and $\Xi^{(NON)}$. The following processes have linear and nonlinear components: the dynamic range of $\Xi^{(LIN)}$ exceeding that of $\Xi^{(NON)}$.

⁵³From Equation 8.

⁵⁴Recall: the \mathcal{L}_{NSE} -operator from Assumption 6; and that the Dirac delta functional is the identity element in the group of \mathbb{R} with respect to the convolution operator.

⁵⁵The D^S -symbol is inspired by Euler notation for iterated-derivative operators, as well as the notation for iterated integrals when writing the differential in vector form [45, 46].

⁵⁶In Equation 48, recall: S_{INP} is that increasing set of $X^{(INP)}$ cyclic-period indices which was introduced in Appendix B.2.

⁵⁷See Definition E.3 regarding the Andrews class.

⁵⁸Definition E.2 on linear/nonlinear decomposition models is inspired by [49]: the models amenable to accurate inference via Multitaper Spectral Analysis.

- $X^{(RES)}$ and $X^{(NSE)}$.
- $X^{(NSW)}$ and $X^{(INP)}$.
- \mathcal{L}_{LAT} is the Dirac delta functional⁵⁹.
- The $X^{(NSE)}$ whitening operator, \mathcal{L}_{NSE} , is given by

$$\mathcal{L}_{NSE} = \kappa_{LOI} \mathcal{D}_{S_{NSE}}, \quad (52)$$

where: κ_{LOI} is constant; and the $\mathcal{D}_{S_{NSE}}$ -operator is itself given by

$$\mathcal{D}_{S_{NSE}} = D^{S_d} D^{|S_{LOI}|} \mathcal{D}_{S_{HII}}. \quad (53)$$

In Equation 53, the $\mathcal{D}_{S_{HII}}$ -operator is given by

$$\mathcal{D}_{S_{HII}} = \langle \delta | L^2 \rangle_{L^2} - \mathcal{L}_S |_{S=S_{HII}}, \quad (54)$$

where \mathcal{L}_S is an operator to be specified forthcoming in Appendix B.4.

- For p_d a d 'th-degree polynomial,

$$D^{|S_{LOI}|} \mathcal{D}_{S_{HII}} g^{(TRD)} = p_d. \quad (55)$$

Moreover, the constant term in $g^{(TRD)}$ is equal to zero.

In Assumption 8, the third list item implies that $X^{(NSW)}$ has weak autocorrelation⁶⁰. The fourth list item implies that $E_{\theta} \circ \Xi(t_n)$ and $\text{Var}_{\theta} \circ \Xi(t_n)$ may both be accurately inferred using the ergodic theorem: treating $\{\Xi^{(LIN)}(t_n)\}_{n=0}^{N-1}$ as if an N -sample drawn from the $\Xi^{(LIN)}(0)$ -distribution [52]. As seen in Equation 55: inclusion of D^{S_d} in the Equations 52 and 53 precludes p_d -effects in $X^{(INP)}$ ⁶¹. Refer to Appendix D.3 for justification introducing the \mathcal{L}_S -operator in Equation 54.

B.3.3 Specification of the Stability Diagnostics

During E_j , the following two stratum-mean dynamical-stability diagnostics are introduced.

1. Micro-epoch scale

The collection,

$$2M_N \{ \bar{\mathbf{f}}_{jk} \}_{k=1}^{K_{PRT}} \subset \mathbb{Z}_{[0, M_N]}^{H_j},$$

of micro-epoch averages. The k 'th element is specified as follows: $\bar{\mathbf{f}}_{jk}[h]$ is the average of eigenfrequency estimates restricted to B_k ⁶².

2. Dynamic-epoch scale

A matrix,

$$2M_N \bar{\mathbf{f}} \in \mathbb{Z}_{[0, M_N]}^{J_{EPC} \times 4},$$

of stratum means. It is given by⁶³

$$\bar{\mathbf{f}}[j, k] = \langle \mathbf{w}_j | \bar{\mathbf{f}}_{jk} \rangle. \quad (56)$$

In Equation 56, the weight vector is itself given by

$$\mathbf{w}_j[h] \|\mathbf{N}_j\|_1 = \mathbf{N}_j[h], \quad (57)$$

where \mathbf{N}_j contains stratum-specific record sizes: $\mathbf{N}_j[h] = N(j, h)$.

⁵⁹Recall the \mathcal{L}_{LAT} -operator from Appendix B.2.

⁶⁰In the terms of Spectral Analysis, one says that $X^{(NSW)}$ has low dynamic range.

⁶¹Removing polynomial trend terms via finite-differencing is a method discussed at length in [4].

⁶²Equation (2.6) in [16].

⁶³Equation (4.2) in [16].

B.4 Metric Generation: Modeling on Discrete Time

Recall from Appendix B.2 the LAT-filter input and output processes: $X^{(INP)}$ and $X^{(NSE)}$, respectively. The Δt -discretization, $\mathcal{X}^{(NSE)}$, of $X^{(NSE)}$ [29, 30, 31, 32] is given by

$$\mathcal{X}^{(NSE)} = \left\{ X^{(NSE)}(t_n) \right\}_{n \in \mathbb{Z}}. \quad (58)$$

Analogously, denote by $\mathcal{X}^{(INP)}$ the Δt -discretization of $X^{(INP)}$. For $\tau \in \mathbb{R}$, call the τ base-time Δt -discretization of any \mathbb{R} -indexed stochastic process that form of the right-hand side of Equation 58 specific to the process in which the following adjustment is made: $t_n \rightarrow t_n + \tau$. The problem is to model $\mathcal{X}^{(NSE)}$ so that it shares features with $X^{(NSE)}$ in terms of the frequency-domain signals that between them characterize the $X^{(NSE)}$ -FDD.

Recall Equation 32 under Assumption 8 that relates the LAT-filter input, $X^{(INP)}$, to the output noise, $X^{(NSE)}$. How to approximate $\mathcal{X}^{(NSE)}$ using this equation? Appendix B.7.2 addresses this problem, and there some use will be made of a new class of stochastic processes forthcoming to be presented Definition B.1 in the present section. . For $J \in \mathbb{N}$, write $S \subset \mathbb{N}_{>1}$ as

$$S = \{s_j\}_{j \in \mathbb{N} \cap (0, J]}. \quad (59)$$

For $\xi \in \mathbb{R}$, the Δ_S -operator is given by

$$\check{\Delta}_S(\xi) = \prod_{s \in S} (1 - \xi^s). \quad (60)$$

The new stochastic-process class is derived from

$$\left| \prod_{s \in S} t_s \right|^{-1} \mathcal{X}^{(NSE)}$$

through the following changes to the \mathcal{L}_{NSE} -specifying operators introduced Appendix B.3.2.

- Low indices:

$$\check{\Delta}_{S_{LOI}}(B) \rightarrow \kappa_{LOI} D^{|S_{LOI}|}.$$

where κ_{LOI} is given by

$$\kappa_{LOI} = \left| \prod_{s \in S} t_s \right|. \quad (61)$$

- High indices: In Equation 52, \mathcal{L}_S on Ξ an L^2 -process is given by

$$\mathcal{L}_S \Xi = \langle \mathcal{I}_S | \mathcal{C}_S \circ \Xi \rangle_{\ell^2}(0), \quad (62)$$

where the APR-component class, \mathcal{C}_S , is given by

$$\mathcal{C}_S \circ \Xi = \left\{ \cos(2\pi f_m \mathbb{R}) \langle \cos(2\pi f_m \mathbb{R}) | \Xi \rangle_{L^2(-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})}(0) \right\}_{m \in \mathbb{Z}}. \quad (63)$$

Having now made the above specifications, it is now possible to define the new class of stochastic processes. Definition B.1 below introduces this class.

Definition B.1. The stochastic process, $X^{(MSR)}$, is multiple SARIMA (MSARIMA)⁶⁴ with $(p, d, q) \times (P, D, Q)$ an ARIMA parameter combination and S aforementioned if:

⁶⁴The superscript in the $\mathcal{X}^{(MSR)}$ -symbol is multiple SARIMA (MSR). Here, there are two acronyms at work: seasonal ARIMA (SARIMA); and autoregressive, integrated moving average (ARIMA).

for all $\tau \in \mathbb{R}$, the τ base-time Δt -discretization of $X^{(MSR)}$ is a solution to the difference equation,

$$\check{\Delta}_S(B) X^{(MSR)}(t_n + \tau) \sim \text{SARIMA}(p, d, q) \times (P, D, Q)_{s_1}. \quad (64)$$

In Equation 64, $P = Q = 0$ and $D = 1$. One writes

$$X^{(MSR)}(t_n + \tau) \sim \text{MSARIMA}(p, d, q) \times (P, D, Q)_S. \quad (65)$$

The MSARIMA model is a natural extension to the SARIMA process for the case that the low-SNR mean-signal element, ν , from Equation 29⁶⁵ is non-vanishing; this point is expanded in the application of Section B.7.2.

B.5 Multitaper Reconstruction of the LFP-oscillation: The Analysis Setup

The multitaper-analysis parameters⁶⁶ were initialized and the $\mathcal{F}_{jh}^{(\eta)}$ -estimates obtained as in [20, 22]. Lowpass-filtering was used to reconstruct the $[0, 90]$ Hz LFP-oscillation: the type of decimation filter depending on E_j as follows.

1. Early/late E_{jh} 's (Type I dynamics): Slepian lowpass⁶⁷.
2. Central E_{jh} 's (dynamics of Types II and III): Chebyshev Type I.

Upon having completed the lowpass-filtering computations, downsampling of the resultant time series was performed in accordance with the reduction in Nyquist frequency required to avoid aliasing [19].

B.6 Inferring the Harmonic and Cyclic Frequencies

This section reviews frequency and cyclic-frequency estimation methods from [19]. The review describes the methods in the context of the time-series models of Section 3.2 and Appendix B.2. Appendices B.6.1 and B.6.2 respectively explain estimation of the eigenfrequencies and the cyclic frequencies.

B.6.1 Time-domain Eigenmodes

Consider from Appendix B.2.1 the signal-plus-noise decomposition the trend term and noise term: $g^{(TRD)}$ and $X^{(NSE)}$, respectively. The following assumption about X signal and noise components is commonplace in spectral analysis when it comes to detecting noise-contaminated eigenmodes.

Assumption 9. The X trendline and noise components are specified as follows.

1. $g^{(TRD)} = z_0$, with $z_m^{(\eta)}$ the m 'th harmonic η -amplitude having been specified in Appendix B.2.2.
2. $X^{(RES)}$ is narrow-sense stationary (NSS).

The $\mathcal{F}_{jh}^{(\eta)}$ -class is inferred the same way as discussed in [20, 22].

⁶⁵Recall Appendix B.2.1.

⁶⁶ M_N ; the multitaper time-bandwidth parameter, NW ; and the number, K_N , of tapers.

⁶⁷Having form similar to that in [23], see [19] for details.

B.6.2 Frequency-domain Eigenmodes

Setup

Consider from Appendix B.2.1: the trend; the high- and low-SNR signal elements; and the noise term. Respectively, these are denoted: g^{TRD} ; η ; ν ; and $X^{(NSE)}$.

Assumption 10. The X mean signal and noise components are specified as follows.

1. Both $g^{(TRD)}$ and η vanish.
2. For III the sampling function, the m 'th low-SNR signal element is an echo signal:

$$\nu_m(t) = \left\langle \text{III} \left| g_m^{(TML)} \right\rangle_{L^2} \left(\frac{f_m}{\Delta t} t \right) \right. \quad (66)$$

where $g_m^{(TML)}$ is a B_{TML} -timelimited (TML) cosine-series signal [43]: the support, B_{TML} , itself given by

$$2f_m B_{TML} = [-1, 1). \quad (67)$$

3. $X^{(NSE)}$ is narrow-sense stationary (NSS).

The second assumption makes sense for the specific purpose of cyclic-frequency inference because periodic components of sharp waveform profile can always be represented either as: realized from an FDD with high skew; or an echo signal. The third assumption is reasonable when: ν explains a significant fraction of $X^{(RES)}$ -cyclostationarity, but none of the ν -eigenmodes become incorporated into η that contains high-SNR eigenmodes identified in low-sensitivity spectral-line statistical detectors⁶⁸. Meanwhile, setting $X^{(NSE)}$ NSS ensures high SNR eigenmodes in the mean of the multitaper power-spectrum reconstruction: on the non-negative part of the principal domain, the natural logarithm of $X^{(NSE)}$ spectral power behaves like a low-order polynomial [6, 18], and so straightforward whitening methods effectively isolate $X^{(INP)}$ spectral power from periodic mean-signal elements of reconstructed power.

Processing and cleaning steps

Just as mentioned in [19]: the set, $\mathcal{F}_{jh}^{(v)}$ - that is to v what $\mathcal{F}_{jh}^{(\eta)}$ is to η - is inferred analogously as $\mathcal{F}_{jh}^{(\eta)}$ in Appendix B.6.1. Instead of applying the relevant statistical detector to \mathbf{x} , the detector is applied to that time series, $\mathbf{l}^{(RES)} \in \mathbb{R}^{M_N}$, containing the log-transformed multitaper $X^{(RES)}$ spectral-power estimators. The starting model assumption is that $\mathbf{l}^{(RES)}$ is realized on the FFT-grid from the $\Delta_N f$ -discretization of a stochastic process, $L^{(RES)}$, on continuous time that is to $\mathbf{l}^{(RES)}$ what X is to \mathbf{x} . From there, the model assumptions of $L^{(RES)}$ are precisely those of Assumption 9, except now with X replaced with $L^{(RES)}$ and all modeling components of X transferring to $L^{(RES)}$ accordingly.

The above methods are applicable if η vanishes, but subtraction of the harmonic term from each of the K_N eigencoefficient spectra⁶⁹ fails to entirely delete the excess harmonic spectral mass within the multitaper neighbourhood band of each eigenfrequency. For an $\mathcal{F}_{jh}^{(\eta)}$ -element, a $[2M_N W]$ -point neighbourhood of the FFT-grid is selected as the site of hard replacement. The hard-replacement reconstruction is a good-neighbours interpolation of the form used in [18], except now with the pilot power-spectrum reconstruction instead being that gapped-taper version from [5].

⁶⁸E.g., the detectors in [22].

⁶⁹For details of this subtraction, refer to: [20, 22].

B.7 Generating the Diagnostic Quantile Curves

This section utilizes the theory of Appendix B.4 to explain how the those novel diagnostic quantile curves⁷⁰ were generated which were introduced Section 3.3.1 and specified in Appendix B.3.1. Appendices B.7.1 and B.7.2 respectively describe the reconstruction methods for the \mathbf{q}_θ -blocks, $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(1)}$ and $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(2)}$. In these sections, reconstructions are performed given the event, $\{\Theta = \theta\}$: the reason being that a realization of Θ is drawn prior to reconstruction in numerical computations of the $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(2)}$ model-uncertainty bounds.

To illustrate the modeling steps for reconstructing $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(2)}$: Figure 5 presents a signal flow graph, with X -components appearing as graph objects. For objects joined together by solid connectors, Table 5 provides an overview of the model assumptions and equations used in the graph construction. As for the triplets of objects joined together by dashed connectors: Assumption 8 alone has been used for the four cases displayed in Figure 5; therefore, Table 6 displays merely the names of the acronyms of superscripts in the $X^{(\#)}$ object labels. In that table, the linear and nonlinear components refer to those specified in Equation 90⁷¹ that is useful for inferring a centrality (mean) and dispersion (standard deviation) parameter associated with X restricted to E_{jh} .

Bottom left, given $\{\Theta = \theta\}$: ψ and ν combine to yield $x^{(SGN)}$. The $x^{(SGN)}$ -signal reaches a junction, and at that point it can proceed through two alternative routes.

1. Rightward

The Gaussian cyclostationary model, discussed in Appendix B.7.1.

2. Upward

The simulation model, discussed in Appendix B.7.2.

Both sections to follow detail between them what remains unexplained of Figure 5.

Table 5: Summary of the Figure 5 relationships associated with graph objects joined together by solid connectors. Here, the ‘‘Assumption’’ column lists the label of the assumption pertaining to the decomposition specification, while the ‘‘Equation(s)’’ column shows where the decomposition has been written out. Meanwhile, ‘‘Label’’ in the first column corresponds to the number enclosed inside the solid-outline box near the relevant decomposition - box colour being the same as that of the connectors involved.

Label	Connector colour			
	Black		Grey	
	Assumption	Equation(s)	Assumption	Equation(s)
1	3	8, 28, 29	6	33
2	5	26	8	51
3	6	32		
4	6	33		

B.7.1 Gaussian Cyclostationary Model: Bounding Curves of the Two-sigma Region

Start with the case that $x^{(SGN)}$ at the junction in Figure 5 moves straight upward. All using black connectors, the signal flow graph shows the following.

⁷⁰ \mathbf{q}_θ from Section 3.3.1.

⁷¹The equation is included in Definition E.2 under Appendix E.

Figure 5: Visual analytics from Signal Processing efficiently summarize the normalization steps in simulating a cyclostationary model used to characterize model uncertainty. Signal flow graph of X in terms of: two state-space models (black/grey, solid lines - see Table 5 referencing explanations of the relationships); and associated linear-ergodic/nonlinear relationships (black, dashed lines). See Table 6 that provides names of the acronyms in superscripts of the form, $X^{(\#)}$.

Table 6: Explanation of superscript of the form in $X^{(\#)}$: in those linear-ergodic/nonlinear decompositions which are depicted in Figure 5. The decomposed component is specified first column, while the Equation 90 linear and nonlinear Ξ -components respectively are specified second and third columns. In the first column, “Label” corresponds to the number enclosed inside the dashed-outline box near the relevant decomposition depicted in the Figure 5 flow graph.

Label	Model component Ξ	Decomposition parts	
		linear (LIN)	nonlinear (NON)
1	input (INP)	linear NSS input (LNI)	nonlinear NSS input (NLI)
2	whitened noise (NSW)	linear NSS whitened (LNW)	nonlinear NSS whitened (NLW)
3	noise (NSE)	linear-noise (LNN)	nonlinear-noise (NLN)
4	residual (RES)	linear-residual (LNR)	nonlinear-residual (NLR)

1. $x^{(SGN)}$ combines with $X^{(NSE)}$ that is coming in from the right: resulting in X that lies below the combination symbol⁷².
2. $X^{(NSE)}$ crosses that filter to its right whose system function is \mathcal{L}_{NSE} (system box, penultimate graph object to the right): the result being the output, $X^{(NSW)}$ ⁷³, below the system box.
3. In the above list item, $X^{(NSW)}$ is LAT: the output of \mathcal{L}_{LAT} (system box, the right-

⁷²Equation 6 in Section 3.2.

⁷³Equation 32 in Appendix B.2.1.

most graph object) given the input, $X^{(INP)}$ (upper right of graph)⁷⁴.

The LAT-model

From Appendix B.4: recall the respective Δt -discretizations, $\mathcal{X}^{(NSE)}$ and $\mathcal{X}^{(INP)}$, of the noise and input processes in the linear whitening model of Equations 32 and 33⁷⁵. In addition, recall that Assumption 7 is imposed to carry out $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(1)}$ -reconstructions. The following assumption ensures that $\mathcal{X}^{(NSE)}$ is LAT.

Assumption 11. $\mathcal{X}^{(NSE)}$ and $\mathcal{X}^{(INP)}$ are related through the causal, invertible expression:

$$X^{(NSE)}(t_n) = \left\langle \mathcal{X}^{(INP)} \middle| \Psi \right\rangle_{\ell^2}(t_n). \quad (68)$$

In Equation 68:

$$\Psi = \{\chi_{(0,\infty)}(j)\Psi_j\}_{j \in \mathbb{Z}}, \quad (69)$$

where Ψ_j is the j 'th linear-representation coefficient of a time-invariant linear filter.

In this manuscript, the problem of reconstructing $X^{(NSE)}$ given $X^{(INP)}$ comes down to inferring parameters of the Ψ transfer function. Inspired both by the signal-plus-noise X decomposition in Appendix B.2.1 and Equations 94 to 97⁷⁶: the estimator, $\hat{\sigma}_\theta(t_n)$, of $\{\Theta = \theta\}$ -conditioned $X(t_n)$ standard deviation is given by⁷⁷

$$\hat{\text{Var}}_\theta \circ X(t_n) = \left\langle \hat{\mathcal{G}}_X^{(NSE)}(0) \middle| \mathcal{C}(t_n; B_v) \right\rangle_{\ell^2}(0). \quad (70)$$

In Equation 70, the m 'th $\hat{\mathcal{G}}_X^{(NSE)}(0)$ -element is denoted $\hat{\gamma}_{X,m}^{(NSE)}(0)$: itself, an estimator for the lag-0 element, $\gamma_{X,m}^{(NSE)}(0)$, of the m 'th $X^{(NSE)}$ rotational cyclic autocorrelation function. This $\gamma_{X,m}^{(NSE)}(0)$ -estimator is given by⁷⁸

$$M_N \hat{\gamma}_{X,m}^{(NSE)}(0) = \left\langle \mathcal{I}_{-M_N B_v \cup M_N B_v} \middle| \hat{\gamma}_Z^{(NSE)}(f_Z, f_Z - f_m) \right\rangle_{\ell^2}(0). \quad (71)$$

In Equation 71, the inverse FFT accounts for the M_N possible frequency estimates given the N data points collected in E_{RCD} ⁷⁹. Also, $\hat{\gamma}_Z^{(NSE)}(f_l, f_l - f_m)$ is given by

$$\hat{\gamma}_Z^{(NSE)}(f_l, f_l - f_m) = \hat{H}(f_l) \overline{\hat{H}(f_l - f_m)} \hat{\gamma}_Z^{(INP)}(f_l, f_l - f_m) \quad (72)$$

where: $\hat{H}(f_m)$ is an estimator of $H(f_m)$ and $\hat{\gamma}_Z^{(INP)}(f_l, f_l - f_m)$ is an estimator of $\gamma_Z^{(INP)}(f_l, f_l - f_m)$ - with $\gamma_Z^{(INP)}$ the $Z^{(INP)}$ rotational autocorrelation function.

Reconstruction

Given Equation 72, the problem is to: infer the H -parameters; and reconstruct $\gamma_Z^{(INP)}$. Once having inferred those parameters, the $\gamma_Z^{(NSE)}$ -reconstruction is obtained substituting the inferred parameters into Equation 72 and then computing Equations 71 then 70. To perform aforementioned inference step requires the following assumption.

⁷⁴Recall: under Assumption 7, \mathcal{L}_{NSE} performs no action on the input.

⁷⁵In Appendix B.2.1.

⁷⁶These equations from Definition E.4 regarding LAT-processes

⁷⁷Equation 70 has been derived from Equation 94 in Definition E.4.

⁷⁸Equation 71 yields a numerical approximation of the spectral representation of that frequency-offset Fourier-transform correlation function specified in Equation 96 whose inverse Fourier-transform signal is the m 'th $X^{(NSE)}$ rotational autocorrelation function.

⁷⁹Recall the set notation introduced for the complex survey Section 3.1.

Assumption 12. The Δt -discretization of $X^{(LNR)}$ is an AR(p)-process whose transfer function is H and whose input is the Δt -discretization of $X^{(LNI)}$.

Assumption 12 permits the use of [18] if one approximates the linear parts with $X^{(RES)}$ and $X^{(INP)}$: p is decided and the AR(p)-process parameters inferred simultaneously from a multitaper $X^{(RES)}$ power-spectrum reconstruction⁸⁰. In turn, one can now make the following specifications for Equation 72.

- $\hat{H}(f_m)$ is that estimator of $H(f_m)$ which is obtained substituting said AR(p)-process parameter estimators into $H(f_m)$.

- Set

$$\hat{\gamma}_Z^{(INP)}(f_l, f_l - f_m) = \hat{\text{Var}}_{\theta} \circ X^{(LNI)}(0), \quad (73)$$

with $\hat{\text{Var}}_{\theta} \circ X^{(LNI)}(0)$ the aforementioned AR(p)-process innovation-variance estimator.

With all coefficient and frequency estimates for Equation 70 readily computed using the multitaper $X^{(RES)}$ power-spectrum reconstruction, the variance-curve reconstruction is obtained precisely in the same manner as is the η -curve reconstruction: the latter reconstruction obtained using the methods of [20, 22].

B.7.2 Integrated-noise Model: The Model-uncertainty Curves

Contrasting with the model in Appendix B.7.1, the model in this section relies on Assumption 8⁸¹ in which it is \mathcal{L}_{LAT} that is made redundant instead of \mathcal{L}_{NSE} . That assumption states that ν_m is an eigenmode, which is tantamount to Assumption 10: that signal which has been truncated to obtain g_m being an amplitude-weighted cosine function. To understand the implications of Assumption 8 on inference and simulation, return to the signal flow graph in Figure 5: the dynamics following upward from aforementioned $x^{(SGN)}$ -junction⁸² outlined as follows, and corresponding to the graph objects joined by grey connectors.

1. As $x^{(SGN)}$ flows rightward, it crosses a diode that blocks $g^{(TRD)} + \nu$ (the permitted signal, η , is written below the diode symbol).
2. η combines with $X^{(RES)}$ that is coming in from the right: resulting in X that lies above the combination symbol⁸³.
3. $X^{(RES)}$ passes the filter to its right whose system function is \mathcal{L}_{NSE} (system box, penultimate graph object to the right): the result being the output, $X^{(INP)}$, drawn above.

The grey, boxed numbers in Figure 5 indicate the order of the following tasks in the simulation required for $\mathbf{q}_{\theta}^{(2)}$ -computations.

1. $X^{(INP)}$ is simulated given different Θ -specifications. Each resulting $X^{(INP)}$ -reconstruction is sent through \mathcal{L}_{NSE}^{-1} to obtain an $X^{(RES)}$ -reconstruction.

⁸⁰The multitaper power-spectrum reconstruction is itself employed in a form of Durbin-Levinson algorithm: a tactic employed frequently in [4], and discussed at length in [18].

⁸¹See Section B.3.2.

⁸²The junction above the ψ/ν -decomposition of $x^{(SGN)}$, bottom-left of the flow graph.

⁸³Equation 6 in Section 3.2.

2. The η -reconstruction is added to each of the resulting $X^{(RES)}$ -reconstructions: yielding X -reconstructions.

Stabilizing state variance

For the Assumption 8 $X^{(INP)}$ -specification to be valid in application, $X^{(INP)}$ (simulated deviates by means of [] using the parameter estimates from *in vivo* data) should have comparable variability to $X^{(NSW)}$ (reconstructed directly from *in vivo* data). That means \mathcal{L}_{NSE} must be a whitening filter explaining a large majority of the $X^{(RES)}$ dynamic range - especially as its transfer function quenches spectral mass at the cyclic frequencies. In Appendix D, it is demonstrated why the integration in an MSARIMA model can cause it to diverge on $\Delta t \mathbb{Z}$ from those \mathbb{R} -indexed time-series models proposed in this manuscript. Without the assured existence of a well-behaved stochastic process accurately interpolating the MSARIMA-process, it becomes harder to justify a tie between the chosen model and the generative Biophysics⁸⁴. Given aforementioned importance of convergent \mathbb{Z} - and \mathbb{R} -indexed time-series models, it is important to ensure that the variabilities of $X^{(NSW)}$ and $X^{(INP)}$ align prior to sending each simulated $X^{(INP)}$ -realization through the \mathcal{L}_{NSE} -filter to generate the $X^{(RES)}$ -reconstruction. Here, the method of achieving said alignment follows the ideas in established works on spectral analysis that stress the importance of normalizing the output of an NSS-process: matching spectral energy to the process variance in the case that the NSS-process happens to be white noise: [3, 35, 48].

The discussion immediately following Assumption 8 explained how the ergodic theorem could be employed for the linear part, $\Xi^{(LIN)}$, of the stochastic process, Ξ , to infer $E_{\theta} \circ \Xi(t_n)$ and $\text{Var}_{\theta} \circ \Xi(t_n)$. Now, employ this inference approach to normalize the reconstructed stochastic processes in that model depicted in Figure 5 whose graph model-component objects are joined together by grey connectors (the ‘‘Grey’’ column of Table 5). Said normalization ensures that the scale of variability in the simulation reconstructions matches that in those data-derived reconstructions which have been used for X -FDD inference.

Table 7 details the normalizations performed, and these rely on Equations 74 and 75 forthcoming. Given an N -point record from each of the equivariant NSS-processes, $\Xi^{(1)}$ and $\Xi^{(2)}$. Even if these two processes were zero-mean, the variability of the processes might be great enough that the N -point record appears to have nonzero mean: being closer in form to the linear-ergodic components - $\Xi_1^{(LIN)}$ and $\Xi_2^{(LIN)}$, respectively to $\Xi^{(1)}$ and $\Xi^{(2)}$ what $\Xi^{(LIN)}$ is to Ξ - that need not have zero mean. Moreover: error propagation incurred during the X -FDD inference steps is significant because one is descending down 2-3 hidden layers of a state model to be able to conduct that inference⁸⁵. Producing the $\Xi^{(2)}$ -reconstruction, $\check{\Xi}^{(2)}$: the normalization expression is

$$\check{\Xi}^{(2)} = \kappa_{NRM} \left\{ X^{(1)} - E_{\theta} \circ \Xi_1^{(LIN)}(0) \right\} + E_{\theta} \circ \Xi_2^{(LIN)}(0). \quad (74)$$

In Equation 74, the normalization (NRM) constant, κ_{NRM} , given by

$$\text{Var}_{\theta} \circ \Xi_2^{(LIN)} = |\kappa_{NRM}|^2 \text{Var}_{\theta} \circ \Xi_1^{(LIN)}, \quad (75)$$

⁸⁴E.g., as in Appendix C: where Equation 85 relates the MEA-output with a filtered cyclostationary process.

⁸⁵Recall the flow graph of Figure 5 that visualizes these layers.

Table 7: The quantities from Table 6 that are used to normalize - via Equations 74 and 75 - variability of the simulated reconstructions to that of the data-derived reconstructions used in X -FDD inference.

$\Xi^{(2)}$	$\Xi^{(1)}$	$\Xi^{(2)}$	$\Xi_1^{(LIN)}$	$\Xi_2^{(LIN)}$
$\check{X}^{(NSW)}$	$X^{(INP)}$	$X^{(NSW)}$	$X^{(LNI)}$	$X^{(LNW)}$
$\check{X}^{(RES)}$	$\check{X}^{(NSE)}$	$X^{(RES)}$	$X^{(LNN)}$	$X^{(LNR)}$

MSARIMA approximation

Denote by \mathbf{s} a vector containing the FFT-quefrequencies: the u 'th entry equal to $t_u \in \Delta t \mathbb{N}_{<M_N}$ - the u 'th $X^{(RES)}$ -quefrecy (i.e., the ν_m period). The vector of cyclic-frequency (CYC) estimates is

$$\mathbf{f}_{CYC} = \text{vec}(\mathcal{F}_{CYC}) \quad (76)$$

where: the vectorizer operator, vec , acts on the class, \mathcal{F}_{CYC} , given by

$$\mathcal{F}_{CYC} = \left\{ f_{m_u} : f_{m_u} \in \left(-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \right] \right\}_{u=1}^{\dim(\mathbf{s})}. \quad (77)$$

In Equation 77: the u 'th FFT-index, m_u , is the nearest to that principal alias which is inferred by $\mathbf{s}[u]$:

$$m_u = \text{ROUND} \left(\frac{t_{M_N}}{\mathbf{s}[u]} \right). \quad (78)$$

Make the $\mathcal{X}^{(RES)}$ approximation,

$$X^{(RES)}(t_n) \sim \text{MSARIMA}(p, d, q) \times (0, 1, 0)_{\tilde{S}_{INP}}. \quad (79)$$

In Equation 79: the set, \tilde{S}_{INP} , of inferred cyclic-period indices is given by

$$\tilde{S}_{INP} = \left\{ \left[(\mathbf{f}_{CYC} [\dim(\mathbf{f}_{CYC}) - u])^{-1} \right] \right\}_{u=0}^{\dim(\mathbf{f}_{CYC})-1}. \quad (80)$$

Equation 79 implies that $\mathcal{X}^{(RES)}$ is governed by a difference equation corresponding to a whitening filter that subtracts out certain trends - in this case, $g^{(TRD)} + \nu$ ⁸⁶.

In light of the Equation 79 approximation, Appendix D.2 justifies why in Appendix B.2 S_{INP} is specified as increasing.

Statistical inference and reconstruction steps

To reconstruct η on $\Delta t \mathbb{Z}_{[0, N]}$, the section-overlap technique of [24] was used. For the ARIMA-parameters, (p, d, q) , the `auto.arima` function of R was utilized with the following settings.

- As recommended in [4] for ARIMA-modeling in general, the following two settings were selected.
 - The Dickey-Fuller test for nonstationarity (affecting d initialization).

⁸⁶Lemma F.2 justifies why $\tilde{\Delta}_{S_{INP}}$ subtracts out the η effects.

– method="ML"
Maximum-likelihood inference method for estimation.

- allowmean=FALSE
According to Assumption 8, assigning zero mean corresponds to $g^{(TRD)}$ having zero constant term.

Each of 100 $X^{(NSE)}$ -reconstructions was computed as follows.

1. Using the methods of [18] for simulating Andrews-class innovations, generate an N -point sequence of random deviates.
2. Enter the simulated innovations sequence from above list item as input for the `simulate` function of R: whose output is the $X^{(NSE)}$ -reconstruction.

Point-by-point on time, the relevant $\mathbf{q}_\theta^{(2)}$ -reconstructions were computed using the empirical distribution function of the 100 $X^{(NSE)}$ -reconstructions.

In Equation 75 that specifies the normalization constant, κ_{NRM} : the following inference techniques were employed.

- Variances were inferred using the average of squared centred time-series values (centering via a sample mean)⁸⁷.
- To within the approximation,

$$\text{Var}_\theta \circ X^{(RES)} \approx \text{Var}_\theta \circ X^{(LNR)}, \quad (81)$$

the sum of squares is computed for entries of the $X^{(RES)}$ -reconstruction vector less: the average of all entries of the MSARIMA $(X^{(RES)} - X^{(NSE)})$ -reconstruction vector⁸⁸.

- To within the approximation,

$$\text{Var}_\theta \circ X^{(NSE)} \approx \text{Var}_\theta \circ X^{(LNN)}, \quad (82)$$

the sum of squares is computed for the $X^{(NSE)}$ -reconstruction vector less the average of the MSARIMA $X^{(NSE)}$ -reconstruction vector entries.

- The assumption of the previous list item was made respectively for $X^{(NSW)}$ and $X^{(INP)}$ with respect to the respective processes, $X^{(LNI)}$ and $X^{(LNU)}$.

C. Biophysical Justification for Cyclostationary Modeling

Here is shown from first principles in Neuroscience the approximations required for X to be APR. Consider the label, $b \in \{e, i\}$: where e and i respectively label an electrode-neighbouring neuron as “excitatory” and “inhibitory” [25]. The local somatic-spike firing rate, Q_b , is a function on spacetime given by [25, 28]

$$\frac{Q_b}{Q_b^{(MAX)}} = \exp \circ \left| V_b^{(STD)} \right|^2 - \exp \circ \left| \frac{1}{\text{CV}_\theta \circ V_b} \right|^2, \quad (83)$$

where the terms are given as follows.

⁸⁷This is a benefit of the ergodic assumption on the linear-NSS decompositions.

⁸⁸This vector reconstructing $g^{(TRD)} + \nu$.

- $Q_b^{(MAX)}$ is the maximum (MAX) of $\{Q_b(t)\}_{t \in \mathbb{R}}$.
- V_b denotes the somatic potential.
- $V_b^{(STD)}$ is V_b standardized (STD).
- CV_{θ} is the coefficient of variation given $\{\Theta = \theta\}$.

A stability analysis of [47] yields the expression,

$$V_b = V_{b,0} + V_{b,1} \cos \circ \phi_b. \quad (84)$$

In Equation 84: $V_{b,0}$ and $V_{b,1}$ are time-homogeneous; while ϕ_b is a nonrandom, time-dependent phase term. Substituting Equation 84 into Equation 83 results in Q_b APR with cyclic frequencies that are multiples of the single V_b cyclic frequency⁸⁹. To account for both the electrostatic effects of local spike firing in a cortical medium and MEA imaging effects: implicitly, the following assumption has been employed throughout this manuscript.

Assumption 13. The LFP-oscillation, X , of MEA-voltage is related to the local somatic-spike firing rate through the expression,

$$X = \mathcal{L}_{LTI} Q_b, \quad (85)$$

where \mathcal{L}_{LTI} is the operator of a linear time-invariant (LTI) filter.

D. MSARIMA Modeling: Considerations

D.1 Low Frequencies: Relationship between the Models on Continuous and Discrete Time

Consider Equation 85 from Appendix C relating: the MEA-voltage LFP-oscillation, X ; and the local somatic-spike firing rate, Q_b . The more similarly operators in an index-limited regime behave like operators in the continuum regime, the more it is possible to tie together: the time-series model; and the spike-firing model of Equation 85. Take $f \in (-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}]$. In Appendix B.7.2, Equation 79 specifies an MSARIMA-model for the Δ -discretization, $\mathcal{X}^{(RES)}$, of the residual X -component, $X^{(RES)}$. The reason for the approximation in Equation 79 is due to limiting behaviour of the transfer function, $H_D^{|S_{LOR}|}$, of that filter whose operator is $D^{|S_{LOR}|}$. Consider the sequence, $\varphi_1(f)$

$$\varphi_1(f) = \{\phi_1(f; \phi_{11})\}_{|\phi_{11}| \in (0,1)}, \quad (86)$$

where: ϕ_1 is the AR(1) transfer function; and ϕ_{11} is the AR(1)-coefficient. Then ($f \rightarrow 0$), Lemma F.3 shows that the $\varphi_1(f)$ -limit as $|\phi_{11}| \rightarrow 1$ is within an $o(f)$ -error of $H_D^{|S_{LOR}|}$. In the time domain, the unit-coefficient limit of an AR(1)-process is an ARIMA(0, 1, 0) process⁹⁰; therefore, the operator of interest is defined through the MSARIMA system function, Δ_S . Specifically, define the estimate, $\check{\Delta}_S$, as ($\xi \in \mathbb{C}$)

$$\check{\Delta}_S(\xi) := \prod_{s \in S} (1 - \xi)^s. \quad (87)$$

⁸⁹i.e., the slope of ϕ_b in Equation 84.

⁹⁰For details about these AR(1)-approximations of nonstationary, integrated-noise processes, refer to [18].

D.2 High Frequencies: The Importance of Differentiation Order

For $s \in S_{LOI}$, Lemma F.5 demonstrates how ($s_J = O(N)$, $N \rightarrow \infty$)

$$\frac{N}{t_{N-1}} \left| \left\{ \left(\prod_{s \in S_{LOI}} t_s \right) D^{|S_{LOI}|} - \Delta_{S_{LOI}}(B) \right\} X^{(NSE)}(t_n) \right| = O_p \circ \sup S_{LOI}. \quad (88)$$

Accuracy of the ARIMA(0, 1, 0)-approximation of stationary integrated noise justifies the choice of S_{INP} increasing. In particular, one interprets the appearance of $D^{|S_{LOI}|}$ in the Equation 53 $\mathcal{D}_{S_{NSE}}$ -specification from Appendix B.3.2 as follows. For $s \in S_{LOI}$, denote by $\mathcal{D}_s^{(LOI)}$ the sequence given by

$$\mathcal{D}_s^{(LOI)} = \left\{ \Delta_{\{s\}}(B) X^{(NSE)}(t_n) \right\}_{n \in \mathbb{Z}}. \quad (89)$$

Remark that $\mathcal{D}_s^{(LOI)}$ is a whitened version of

$$\left\{ X^{(NSE)}(t_{ks}) \right\}_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} :$$

containing no trace of linear trends interpolating $\mathcal{D}_s^{(LOI)}$. When $s = \sup S_{LOI}$, the linear trends span longer stretches of the record window; therefore, subtracting these trends out leaves behind the higher-frequency trends. As $s \downarrow \inf S_{LOI}$, each shorter-duration linear trend may be thought of as a MacLaurin approximation of a longer-duration, higher-frequency trend.

Preservation of the relationship between $X^{(NSE)}$ and $X^{(NSW)}$ under the action of Δt -discretization satisfies the objective outlined in the first paragraph of Appendix B: that $\mathcal{X}^{(NSE)}$ be modeled in order for it to share frequency-domain features with $X^{(NSE)}$.

D.3 Low Frequencies: Subtracting Out the APR-component

Recall $\check{\Delta}_S$ from Appendix D.1. From Lemma F.4 ($s_1 = O(N)$, $N \rightarrow \infty$), $t_N^{-1} \text{Log} \circ \check{\Delta}_{S_{HII}}$ is within an $O\left(\frac{s_J}{N}\right)$ difference of $t_N^{-1} \text{Log} \circ \Delta_{S_{HII}}$. Since N is finite and s_J can have the same scale as N , the discrepancy is just as inappropriate in this case as that corresponding to the estimation in Equation 88 from Appendix D.2 when it comes to justifying the $\check{\Delta}_S$ approximation of Δ_S . Therefore, Equation 52 from Appendix B.3.2 incorporates the operator, $1 - \mathcal{L}_S$, instead. In Equation 33 from Appendix B.2.1, that operator directly subtracts the APR-component from $X^{(NSE)}$: precisely the same action that the operator, Δ_S , performs on ν under Assumption 8⁹¹.

E. Definitions

Definition E.1. The signal elements of a stochastic process are its nonrandom additive components.

Definition E.2. Indexed on continuous time: a stochastic process, Ξ , is said to have linear (LIN) and nonlinear (NON) components if it has the decomposition,

$$\Xi = \Xi^{(LIN)} + \Xi^{(NON)}. \quad (90)$$

where $\Xi^{(LIN)}$ - the linear component - is ergodic (though, not necessarily zero-mean), and where $\Xi^{(NON)}$ is a nonlinear component.

⁹¹Proof for this statement is provided in Lemma F.2.

Definition E.3. The Andrews class consists of distributions from the following families⁹²: Gaussian; Gumbel; Logistic; Student; and Uniform. Of said families, only distributions are retained whose parameters are defined such that the mean is equal to zero and the variances of the different distributions are all equal to a single value.

Definition E.4. To say that $X^{(NSE)}$ from Appendix B.2 is LAT means that it has the representation⁹³,

$$X^{(NSE)} = \left\langle \mathcal{I}_{A_{NSE}} \left| \left\langle \mathcal{G}^{(MOD)} \left| X^{(INP)} \right\rangle_{L^2} \right\rangle_{\ell^2} (0), \quad (91)$$

where the terms are given as follows.

- The index set, A_{NSE} , is given by

$$A_{NSE} = -E_{NSE} \cup \{0\} \cup E_{NSE}, \quad (92)$$

where $E_{NSE} \subset \mathbb{N}$.

- The class of modulators (MOD), $\mathcal{G}^{(MOD)}$, is given by

$$\mathcal{G}^{(MOD)} = \{ h_m \exp(i2\pi f_m \mathbb{R}) \}_{m \in \mathbb{Z}}, \quad (93)$$

where h_m is the m 'th time-invariant filter function.

- $X^{(INP)}$ is a cyclostationary input (INP) process whose cyclic-period set, B_v , is equal to that of $X^{(NSE)}$.

For \mathbf{q}_θ , only that subclass of LAT processes is employed whose filters are time-invariant: $E_{NSE} = \emptyset$, and h_0 denoted by h . The $X^{(NSE)}$ rotational autocorrelation function, $\gamma_X^{(NSE)}$, is given by⁹⁴

$$\gamma_X^{(NSE)}(t, t + \tau) = \left\langle \mathcal{G}_X^{(NSE)}(\tau) \left| \mathcal{C}(t; \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}) \right\rangle_{\ell^2} (0). \quad (94)$$

In Equation 94, the terms are given as follows.

- $\mathcal{G}_X^{(NSE)}(\tau)$ contains the X rotational cyclic autocorrelation functions - each evaluated at lag, τ .
- $\mathcal{C}(t; A)$ contains cosine functions - each evaluated at time, t :

$$\mathcal{C}(t; A) := \left\{ \chi_A(m) \cos \left(2\pi f_m \frac{t}{\Delta t} \right) \right\}_{m \in \mathbb{Z}} \quad (95)$$

Denote by $\gamma_{X,m}^{(NSE)}$ the m 'th rotational autocorrelation function of X . It is the inverse-Fourier-transform signal of $\gamma_{Z,m}^{(OFS)}$ ⁹⁵: itself, the frequency-offset (OFS) function associated with $\gamma_Z^{(NSE)}$ that is given by

$$\gamma_{Z,m}^{(OFS)}(f) = \gamma_Z^{(NSE)}(f, f - f_m). \quad (96)$$

In Equation 96, $\gamma_Z^{(NSE)}$ is the rotational autocorrelation function of the Fourier-transform process, $Z^{(NSE)}$, of $X^{(NSE)}$. The Fourier-transform process is given by⁹⁶

$$Z^{(NSE)} = H Z^{(INP)}, \quad (97)$$

with H and $Z^{(INP)}$ respectively the Fourier-transform signal of h and Fourier-transform process of $X^{(INP)}$.

⁹²As stated in [18]: strong-mixing, first-order autoregressive processes having innovations of the judgment sample of [1] may have eigencefficient spectra exhibiting proper, joint-spherical FDD. The name of the class has been chosen to credit the expert - Andrews, author of cited work - who decided on said judgment sample.

⁹³Equations (1.112-1.113) in [32].

⁹⁴Equation (1.123) in [32].

⁹⁵Equation(1.124) in [32].

⁹⁶Equation(1.123) in [32].

F. Lemmas

Lemma F.1. For $s \in \mathbb{N}$, the ν_m -frequency is invariant under the action of $\check{\Delta}_{\{s\}}$ on ν_m .

Lemma F.2. The stochastic process, X , satisfies

$$\check{\Delta}_S X(t_n) = \check{\Delta}_S \{X(t_n) - \langle \mathcal{I}_S | \nu_{\mathbb{Z}}(t_n) \rangle_{\ell^2}(0)\}. \quad (98)$$

Lemma F.3. For $S \subset \mathbb{N}$, define U_S as

$$U_S := \langle \mathcal{I}_S | \mathbb{Z} \rangle_{\ell^2}(0). \quad (99)$$

Recalling ϕ_1 and ϕ_{11} from Section D.1 ($f \rightarrow 0$),

$$\lim_{\phi_{11} \rightarrow 1} \phi_1^{U_S} \circ \exp(i2\pi f) = H_D^S(f) + o(f). \quad (100)$$

Lemma F.4. For $\xi \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \{1\}$ ($s_1 = O(N)$, $N \rightarrow \infty$):

$$\frac{1}{t_N} \left| \check{L}_S(f) - \text{Log} \circ \check{\Delta}_S \circ \exp(i2\pi f) \right| = O\left(\frac{s_J}{N}\right), \quad (101)$$

where the function, \check{L}_S , is given by

$$\check{L}_S(f) = \text{Log} \circ \check{\Delta}_S \circ \exp(i2\pi f). \quad (102)$$

Lemma F.5. The Δ_S -operator is related to D through the expression ($s_J = o(N)$, $N \rightarrow \infty$),

$$\frac{1}{t_N} \left\{ D^J - \left| \prod_{s \in S} t_s \right|^{-1} \Delta_S(B) \right\} X^{(NSE)}(t_n) = o_p\left(\frac{s_J}{N}\right). \quad (103)$$

G. Proofs

Proof. **Lemma F.1**

Using Euler's identity for the cosine function, ν_m satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} \check{\Delta}_{\{s\}} \nu_m(t_n) &= \left| z_m^{(\nu)} \right| \left\{ \frac{e^{i2\pi f_m n} + e^{-i2\pi f_m n}}{2} - \frac{e^{i2\pi f_m [n-s]} + e^{-i2\pi f_m [n-s]}}{2} \right\} \\ &= \left| z_m^{(\nu)} \right| \left\{ \frac{e^{i2\pi f_m n} - e^{i2\pi f_m [n-s]}}{2} + \frac{e^{-i2\pi f_m n} - e^{-i2\pi f_m [n-s]}}{2} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (104)$$

Using trigonometric identities, obtain

$$\begin{aligned} e^{i2\pi f_m n} - e^{i2\pi f_m (n-s)} &= e^{i2\pi f_m n} \left(1 - e^{-i2\pi f_m s} \right) \\ &= 2i \sin(\pi |s f_m|) \exp\left(i2\pi f_m \left[n - \frac{s}{2}\right]\right). \end{aligned} \quad (105)$$

Substituting into the final line of Equations 104 the final line of Equations 105:

$$\begin{aligned}
I & := \check{\Delta}_{\{s\}} \nu_m(t_n) \\
& = i \left| z_m^{(\nu)} \right| \sin(\pi f_{sm}) \left[\exp \left(i 2\pi f_m \left[n - \frac{s}{2} \right] \right) - \exp \left(-i 2\pi f_m \left[n - \frac{s}{2} \right] \right) \right] \\
& = 2 \left| z_m^{(\nu)} \right| \sin(\pi f_{sm}) \sin \left(2\pi f_m \left[\frac{s}{2} - n \right] \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{106}$$

Therefore, $\check{\Delta}_{\{s\}} \nu_m$ has the same frequency, f_m , as ν_m . \square

Proof. Lemma F.2

From Lemma F.1, the ν_m -frequency is invariant to $\Delta_{\{s\}}$. On $\Delta t \mathbb{Z}$, differentiating by $\Delta_{\{s\}}$ the process,

$$X - \langle \mathcal{I}_{S \setminus \{s\}} \mid \nu_{\mathbb{Z}} \rangle_{\ell^2}(0),$$

yields the right-hand side of Equation 98. \square

Proof. Lemma F.3

For ζ given by

$$\zeta = e^{-i2\pi f}. \tag{107}$$

the transfer function, H_D^S , satisfies ($f \rightarrow 0$)

$$\begin{aligned}
H_D^S(f) & = \Delta_S(\bar{\zeta}) \\
& = \text{Arg}^{U_S}(\bar{\zeta}) \\
& = (1 - \zeta)^{U_S} + o \circ \left\langle \mathcal{I}_{[1, U_S]} \mid \mathcal{G}_{U_S}^{(BIN)}(1 - \zeta, f) \right\rangle_{\ell^2}(0) \\
& = \lim_{\phi_{11} \rightarrow 1} \phi_1^{U_S}(\bar{\zeta}) + o \circ \left\langle \mathcal{I}_{[0, U_S]} \mid \mathcal{G}_{U_S}^{(BIN)}(f, f) \right\rangle_{\ell^2}(0) - o(f^{U_S}) \\
& = \lim_{\phi_{11} \rightarrow 1} \phi_1^{U_S}(\bar{\zeta}) + o(f).
\end{aligned} \tag{108}$$

In Equations 108, $\mathcal{G}_K^{(BIN)}$ is a sequence of binomial-expansion (BIN) functions: given for $z \in \mathbb{C}$ by

$$\mathcal{G}_K^{(BIN)}(z, f) = \left\{ \binom{K}{u} z^{K-u} f^{2u} \right\}_{u \in \mathbb{Z}}. \tag{109}$$

The second of Equations 108 arises from combining the Fourier-transform convolution and derivative theorems. The third line has been obtained having: substituted for the first term in the first line the MacLaurin expansion for the polynomial argument; invoked the binomial theorem for the expansion that is raised to the power of U_S in the resultant expression; and set aside the $u = 0$ term out up front. As for the fourth line, the second term arises from a substitution in second line of aforementioned $1 - e^{-i2\pi f}$ MacLaurin expansion. The final line arises having invoked the binomial theorem for the second term of the third line. \square

Proof. **Lemma F.4**

Define ξ as

$$\xi = e^{i2\pi f}. \quad (110)$$

In addition, define the approximating set, \check{S} , of S as

$$\check{S} := \{s + [1 - s \bmod 2]\}_{s \in S}. \quad (111)$$

In Equation 111, the \check{S} -integer estimating s is only not equal to s if s is even: in which case, s is incremented because that way one additional differencing step ensures yet more whitening and yet more reason to use ARIMA-modeling on the whitened filter output.

For Equation 87 from Appendix D.1, invoking the binomial theorem together with $\mathcal{G}_K^{(BIN)}$ from Equation 109 in the proof of Lemma F.3, yields the expression,

$$\begin{aligned} \check{L}_{\check{S}}(f) &= \left\langle \mathcal{I}_{\check{S}} \left| \text{Log} \circ \mathcal{H}_{\mathcal{A}_1}^{(BIN)}(1; \xi) \right. \right\rangle_{\ell^2}(0) \\ &= \left\langle \mathcal{I}_{\check{S}} \left| \text{Log} \circ \mathcal{H}_{\mathcal{A}_2}^{(BIN)}(\xi; \xi) \right. \right\rangle_{\ell^2}(0) \\ &= \text{Log} \circ \Delta_{\check{S}}(\xi) + \check{L}_S^{(RES)}(f). \end{aligned} \quad (112)$$

In Equations 112: the sequence, $\mathcal{H}_{\mathcal{A}}^{(BIN)}(z; \xi)$, for $(z, u) \in \mathbb{C} \times \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ is given by

$$\mathcal{H}_{\mathcal{A}}^{(BIN)}(z; \xi) = \left\{ \left\langle \mathcal{I}_{A_u} \left| \mathcal{G}_u^{(BIN)}(-\xi, 1) \right. \right\rangle_{\ell^2}(0) + \left\langle \mathcal{I}_{[0, u] \setminus A_u} \left| \mathcal{G}_u^{(BIN)}(-\xi, 1) \right. \right\rangle_{\ell^2}(0) \right\}_{u \in \mathbb{Z}}. \quad (113)$$

In Equation 113, the u 'th \mathcal{A} -element is denoted A_u . Moreover: each \mathcal{A}_1 -element is equal to \emptyset ; while $A_u = \{0, u\}$ for the u 'th \mathcal{A}_2 -element. In Equations 112, the residual function, $\check{L}_S^{(RES)}$, is given by

$$\check{L}_S^{(RES)}(f) = \langle \mathcal{I}_{\check{S}} \left| \text{Log}(1 + z_{\mathbb{Z}}) \right. \rangle_{\ell^2}(0). \quad (114)$$

In Equation 114, z_s is given by

$$z_s = \frac{1}{1 - \xi^s} (-1)^k \binom{s}{k} \xi^k. \quad (115)$$

In Equations 112, the second line arises from the first because all \check{S} -elements are odd: $(-1)^s = 1$. Now, explore the behaviour of $\check{L}_S^{(RES)}$ in the $s \rightarrow \infty$ limit. Invoking monotonicity,

$$\begin{aligned} |z_s| &\leq \frac{1}{|1 - \xi^s|} \left\langle \mathcal{I}_{[1, s]} \left| \mathcal{G}_s^{(BIN)}(1, 1) \right. \right\rangle \\ &= 2 \frac{2^{s-1} - 1}{|1 - \xi^s|}. \end{aligned} \quad (116)$$

In Equations 116, the second line arises from the binomial theorem. In addition ($s_1 \rightarrow \infty$),

$$z_s = O\left(\frac{2^s}{|1 - \xi^s|}\right). \quad (117)$$

Next, remark that the denominator in Equation 117 satisfies

$$|1 - \xi^s| = 2 [1 - \cos(2\pi f s)]. \quad (118)$$

Therefore, z_s behaves as $O(2^s)$ as $s \rightarrow \infty$, and so

$$\text{Log}(1 + z_s) = (\ln 2) s + \text{Log} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2^s} \right). \quad (119)$$

From [10], the second term right-hand side of Equation 119 satisfies

$$\text{Log} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2^s} \right) = \frac{1}{2^s} + O \left(\frac{1}{2^{2s}} \right). \quad (120)$$

The above calculations permit the following writing of Equation 114:

$$\check{L}_S^{(RES)}(f) = O(s_J). \quad (121)$$

□

Proof. Lemma F.5

The first backward difference approximation yields⁹⁷

$$\frac{1}{t_{N-1}} DX^{(NSE)}(t_n) = \frac{1}{t_{N-1}} \frac{1}{t_{s_J}} \Delta_{\{s_J\}}(B) X^{(NSE)}(t_n) + o_p \left(\frac{s_J}{N-1} \right). \quad (122)$$

Repeating the above finite-difference approximation for the second derivative yields

$$\frac{1}{t_{N-1}} D^2 X^{(NSE)}(t_n) = \frac{1}{t_{N-1} t_{s_{J-1}} t_{s_J}} \Delta_{\{s_{J-1}, s_J\}}(B) X^{(NSE)}(t_n) + o_p \left(\frac{s_J}{N} \right). \quad (123)$$

Inference based on the pattern of Equations 122 and 123 gives rise to Equation 103.

□

⁹⁷Equation (5.6) in [14].